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LILAS4SOILS

CARBON FARMING

LILAS4SOILS D4.1 –Protocol for sampling design, soil sample preprocessing and analysis, and monitoring changes in soil organic carbon stock and soil health indicators

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Version: Second Version – ***This is a draft version subject to the approval of EC.***

Submission Date: 10/11/2025

Dissemination level: PU

Grant Agreement N°: 101157414

Starting Date: 01-09-2024

Duration: 60 months

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Abbreviations

AFRSS	Area-Frame Randomized Soil Sampling
C	Carbon
CF	Carbon farming
cLHS	Conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling
CRCF	Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming
CRS	Coordinate Reference System
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
IS	Independent synchronous
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GIS	Geographic information system
LL	Living lab
LUCAS	Land Use/Cover Area frame statistical Survey
MAOM	Mineral-associated organic matter
MDD	Minimum detectable difference
MRV	Monitoring, reporting and verification
NDVI	Normalized difference vegetation index
PMN	Potential mineralizable nitrogen
POM	Particulate organic matter
RP	Rotating panel
SA	Serially alternating
SIC	Soil inorganic carbon
SOC	Soil organic carbon
SOM	Soil organic matter
SP	Supplemented panel
SRS	Simple random sampling
SS	Static-synchronous
TC	Total carbon
TWI	Topographic wetness index

Executive Summary

This document is the second version of deliverable 4.1, which supports the planning and implementation of soil sampling design across participant demo sites from five living labs in the context of LILAS4SOILS (*Fostering Carbon Farming Practices through Living LABs in the Mediterranean & Southern EU for the healthy future of European SOILS*). The target end-users of the soil sampling and data collection protocol are the living lab coordinators and team who will carry the field sampling and data management at living lab level. The deliverable also contributes to the growing body of publicly available protocols for soil sampling and methodologies for monitoring SOC changes, which can be of interest to other researchers, land managers or consultants interested in setting up carbon farming projects. The deliverable includes field and laboratory protocols to measure other soil properties beyond soil organic carbon stocks, indicators of several soil functions.

The deliverable is structured by 1) providing a brief introduction to the objectives of LILAS4SOILS and some aspects of space-time monitoring of soil organic carbon and link between soil indicators and functions, followed by 2) an overview of some methods for soil spatial sampling approaches, 3) specific protocols for spatial sampling design, field sampling, and laboratory analyses within LILAS4SOILS, and 4) calculations for estimating SOC stocks and changes in SOC stocks over time. Finally, there is a short tutorial for implementing spatial sampling with the free and open software R, and examples of templates to register fieldwork notes.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Alexandre M.J.-C. Wadoux (INRAE, France), Andrea Ferrarini (UNICATT, Italy), Jose Luis Gabriel Pérez (CSIC, Spain) and Benjamín Sánchez Gimeno (CSIC, Spain) for their valuable help with spatial soil sampling strategies at the early stages of designing this protocol.

There were many improvements and additions to the previous version of this protocol that would not have been possible without the feedback provided by the LILAS4SOILS External Expert Advisory Board members Edoardo A.C. Costantini (CNR-IBE) and Senani Karunaratne (CSIRO), and the thorough revisions by external reviewers Marta Gómez Giménez (MRV4SOC), Timo Breure (EC), Ruth Pereira, (UPorto), Maëva Labouyrie (EC, JRC), Martino Martins (University of Aveiro, Portugal), Frederik Bøe (NIBIO), Jannes Stolte (NIBIO), Inbar Morag (NIBANNA), Nicolas Saby (INRAE), and the feedback from more than 50 participants of the online workshop held on 17 June 2025 dedicated to discuss the general alignment of the protocol with the EU Soil Monitoring Law (SML) and the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming regulation (CRCF).

This document is a draft version for expert consultation and subject to the approval of the European Commission.

1. Introduction

Soils are the main reservoir of carbon in terrestrial ecosystems (Dixon et al., 1994), with a combined pool of organic and inorganic carbon (C) of approximately four times the atmospheric C pool and seven times the biotic C pool (Lal, 2010). The global soil organic carbon (SOC) stock for the first metre of soil is estimated in 1500 Pg C (Jobbágy and Jackson, 2000) with other estimates ranging from 504 to 3000 Pg C (Scharlemann et al., 2014). The soil carbon stocks increase to 2400 Pg C for SOC (Batjes, 1996) and more than 2300 Pg for soil inorganic carbon (SIC) in the first two metres (Zamanian et al., 2021). Soils can be a sink or a source of C. Hence, even small changes in SOC dynamics and storage can alter the ecosystem C balance with an impact on atmospheric CO₂ levels at the regional scale. The global C budget for 2023 estimated the net uptake of CO₂ by the land on 2.3 ± 1.0 Gt C yr⁻¹, while fossil emissions were 10.1 ± 0.5 Gt C yr⁻¹ and land use change emissions 1.0 ± 0.7 Gt C yr⁻¹ (Friedlingstein et al., 2025). Zickfeld et al. (2023) advised that reducing CO₂ or greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions should be prioritised over removals if we aim to achieve the goal of the Paris Agreement to limit global warming well below 2°C and to pursue efforts to limit warming to 1.5°C relative to pre-industrial levels. The rationale is that the effects of both processes (emissions and removals) on climate may not be equivalent due to differences in their biogeophysical effects, impermanence of sequestered C, non-CO₂ GHG and aerosol effects, and nonlinearities of the Earth system (Zickfeld et al., 2023). They posit that carbon neutrality may not mean climate neutrality. The implementation of removal technologies (including land use change and reforestation and afforestation practices, and C sequestration in the soil through agricultural practices) to an extent needed to achieve climate goals may not be feasible due to biophysical and economic constraints (Smith et al., 2016). Rather than promoting soil C sequestration as a universal remedy to compensate fossil emissions, the scientific community, agriculture and land managers, and different stakeholders should emphasize the beneficial effects of enhancing soil C sequestration on overall soil health and functions (Baveye et al., 2018). Indeed, the central role of SOC for soil multifunctionality encourages the adoption of agricultural practices increasing SOC storage (Kopittke et al., 2022). International initiatives like “4 per 1000” (<https://4p1000.org/>) aim at sequestering C from the atmosphere while enhancing soil functions and services, notably food security and resilience and adaptation to climate change.

Carbon farming (CF) encompasses several sustainable agricultural and forestry practices that target the reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from soils and enhance C storage in soils and biomass. Besides the positive effects on climate change abatement and soil health, CF may become an additional source of income for farmers and foresters by the participation in voluntary C credit markets. The EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Certification Regulation (European Parliament, Council of the European Union, 2024) laid the grounds for establishing the first EU-wide voluntary framework for certifying C removals, CF and carbon storage in products across Europe. Some carbon farming practices (CFPs) that are considered by the CRCF (Directorate-General for Climate Action, European Commission, 2025) and that can be applicable to the Mediterranean context include:

- Peatland management. Rewetting and restoring previously drained peatlands, keeping existing peatlands in good conservation status to avoid emissions, and adapted management of drained peatlands currently destined to productive uses which cannot be restored.
- Agroforestry and mixed farming. Increasing silvoarable and silvopastoral systems, integrating trees or shrubs with crop and/or livestock management, presence of hedgerows or field boundary tree cover.
- Improved fertilizer use efficiency management to reduce nitrous gas emissions (nutrient planning, use of nitrification inhibitors).

- Soil protection and SOC management practices like cover crops, conservation tillage, improved crop rotations, organic farming, etc.
- Reforestation respecting ecological principles for biodiversity and sustainable forest management.
- Livestock management. Grazing and grassland management, reducing enteric methane by improving feed digestibility and efficiency, reducing NO emissions through manure management.

These CFPs have the potential to sequester C and reduce GHG emissions, become an additional income source for farmers, and enhance soil health and multifunctionality.

1.1 Synergies and trade-offs between SOC storage and other soil functions

There are several frameworks and definition of soil functions. Soil functions have been broadly defined as “bundles of soil processes that underpin the delivery of ecosystem services” (Bünemann et al., 2018). Evangelista et al. (2023) provide a list of soil functions that are an extension of those defined by Blum (2005) and the European Commission (Commission of the European Communities, 2006). According to Evangelista et al. (2023) the soil is:

- A producer of food and biomass.
- A store of carbon.
- A habitat for, and of, biodiversity.
- A store and regulator of nutrients.
- A store, purifier and regulator of water.
- A filter and remediator of contaminants.
- A source of raw materials.
- An archive of archæological artefacts.

The quantitative assessment of soil functions is complex, but a common element of different approaches begins with the identification of a minimum set of relevant indicators. These indicators are soil properties (dynamic or static) that inform of the soil potential and current performance of a function for given local conditions and management (Bünemann et al., 2018; Drobniak et al., 2018; Vogel et al., 2019). The list of indicators for soil functions, soil health and related concepts is quite extensive, but SOC or SOC related properties are common among all lists.

SOC is the main component of soil organic matter (SOM) and is considered a general indicator of soil quality and soil health due to its correlation with multiple soil properties and critical role for soil functions, resilience and resistance to pressures (Herrick and Wander, 1998). SOM influences physical soil properties like compactability, friability and increases soil water retention attributes, although the positive effect on available water capacity may be more limited than previously estimated (Minasny and McBratney, 2018). The interactions between plant roots, soil biota and SOC develop soil aggregates and structure, regulating air and water infiltration and movement through the profile, soil permeability and erodibility. The predominantly negative charge of organic matter’s functional groups contributes to the soil cation exchange capacity, and weak acidic functional groups contribute to the soil buffering capacity, influencing the function of nutrient storage and regulation. SOM has high sorption capacity for several pollutants and heavy metals, leading to their immobilisation and preventing the contamination of groundwater and bioavailability, supplying the soil function of filter and remediator of contaminants (Kwiatkowska-Malina, 2018).

Vrebos et al. (2021) assessed the trade-offs and synergies between soil functions in agricultural lands from different pedoclimatic zones in Europe. Across the entire European Union, the function of climate regulation was positively correlated with drought protection and water purification and negatively correlated with waterlogging protection and nutrient cycling. The sign and magnitude of correlations between soil functions vary among climatic zones and land uses (e.g., arable land and grasslands) (Vrebos et al., 2021; Zwetsloot et al., 2021). For example, Zwetsloot et al. (2021) found positive correlations between climate regulation and biodiversity in grasslands and arable land in the Pannonian climatic region, whereas in Atlantic arable land the correlation between climate regulation and biodiversity was negative. Hence, there is a need to assess the potential trade-offs and synergies between C sequestration and other functions in the Mediterranean context associated to carbon farming projects.

A set of soil health indicators and soil properties used as input for process-based models will be measured simultaneously to SOC stocks, namely: particle size distribution, coarse fragments, bulk density, SOC, TC, total nitrogen, carbonates, pH, electrical conductivity (EC), potential mineralizable nitrogen (PMN), SOM fractions, soil moisture at field water capacity and at permanent wilting point, and 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing. The rationale behind this choice is explained in Table 1, although we acknowledge that the list of indicators is not as exhaustive as in other studies. There are several resources to select the indicators more adequate to the objectives and management needs of the local stakeholders such as the Biological Soil Information System (<https://biosisplatform.eu/>), which gives emphasis to the role of soil biota in soil processes and functions. Selection of indicators is often done with a logical sieve (Ritz et al., 2009) or based on expert opinion (Zwetsloot et al., 2022).

Table 1: Soil properties selected as soil health indicators, and parameters used to estimate SOC stocks and model C dynamics.

Soil indicator	Justification	Soil functions
Particle size distribution	Soil texture influences several soil processes and functions. The content of clay and fine silt particles is recognized as a proxy for the capacity to protect SOC against decomposition through physico-chemical stabilization mechanisms (Lützow et al., 2006; Six et al., 2002). Particle size distribution influences the architecture of the mineral matrix and is related to porosity and aeration, water infiltration and storage (Cousin et al., 2022). Particle size distribution in interaction with soil biota is related to aggregate and soil structure development, which in turn influences the capacity for root development and plant growth, and water movement through the soil. Parameters used for process-based modelling of ecosystem C dynamics with the ARMOSA model (Perego et al., 2013).	Carbon storage Water quality, regulation and storage
Coarse fragments	The content of coarse fragments is needed for the calculation of SOC stocks. Generally, this variable has high spatial heterogeneity and is hard to predict. Overlooking the content of coarse fragments can lead to large errors in the estimation of SOC stocks, especially in stony soils (Poeplau et al., 2017).	Carbon storage
Bulk density	Bulk density is a proxy of compaction, which can be a limiting factor for water infiltration and movement, aeration, waterlogging, root growth and hence crop yield. Bulk density is used to calculate SOC stocks. It is a dynamic soil property, sensitive to agricultural management.	Water quality, regulation and storage Carbon storage Biomass production
Soil Organic Carbon	SOC is widely accepted as a universal soil health indicator because of the relationships with multiple soil properties and processes. The more evident function is carbon storage, but it also influences water storage and quality, nutrient storage and regulation as it is important for the cation exchange capacity and nutrients in the solution exchange that are available for plants, hence influence biomass productions.	Carbon storage Nutrient storage and regulation Biomass production

		Water quality, regulation and storage
Total Carbon	TC includes soil inorganic carbon (SIC) and SOC, resulting on the total carbon storage.	Carbon storage
Total Nitrogen	Total nitrogen can be interpreted as the total reservoir of N in the soil, in available and unavailable forms for plants, hence used as a proxy for soil fertility and nutrient storage, availability and regulation. The microbial-mediated processes of SOC stabilization are dependent on the stoichiometry of the soil organic matter.	Nutrient storage and regulation Carbon storage
Carbonates	Soil inorganic carbon is an important component of the total carbon stock in Mediterranean and semi-arid environments (Shariffar et al., 2023).	Carbon storage
pH	pH regulates the availability of cations in the soil exchange solution, influences the cation exchange capacity. It is a master soil property that also controls the dominant mechanisms of SOC stabilization, e.g., cation bridging or calcium-mediated stabilization in more calcareous environments (Rasmussen et al., 2018; Rowley et al., 2018).	Nutrient storage and regulation
Electrical conductivity (EC)	EC can be used as an early warning sign for incipient salinity, which happens often in irrigated systems in the Mediterranean. Rather than indicator of a soil function, it is indicator of a potential <i>threat</i> to soil.	Water quality, regulation and storage
Potential Mineralizable Nitrogen (PMN)	Good correlation with microbial biomass and total soil N (Bünemann et al., 2018)	Nutrient storage and regulation
Soil organic matter fractions (MAOM and POM)	<p>Soil organic matter is composed by varying compounds along a gradient of chemical composition, mean residence time, protection against decomposition, origin, etc. Fractionation methods attempt to separate pools with supposedly different residence time and degree of stabilization.</p> <p>MAOM is predominantly composed of low-molecular-weight molecules of microbial origin (e.g. microbial metabolites, necromass), leachates from plant litter, and rhizodeposition, which are protected through sorption to mineral surfaces or occluded inside microaggregates. MAOM has a lower C:N ratio, a higher proportion of microbial derived and proteinaceous compounds and a longer mean residence time (decades to centuries). Hence, it is relevant for carbon storage.</p> <p>POM is mainly composed of partially decomposed plant litter and roots and fungal-derived compounds that can be found free or inside macroaggregates. POM has higher C:N ratio than MAOM, and shorter mean residence time (years to decades), so it is more important for nutrient cycling and regulation.</p>	Carbon storage Nutrient storage and regulation
Soil moisture at field water capacity (θ_{FC})	Soil water content after rapid drainage, linked to dominance of gravity over capillary forces. Upper limit of the available water capacity (AWC, the maximum quantity of water that soil can theoretically store), related to water availability to plants. Common values of θ_{FC} are determined for matric potential of -33 kPa or -10 kPa.	Water quality, regulation and storage
Soil moisture at permanent wilting point (θ_{WP})	Soil moisture content at a point where plants wilt and cannot longer recover turgidity. In field conditions it varies per crop type or vegetation, but it is generally characterized for -1500 kPa. It is the lower limit of AWC, strongly controlled by soil texture. Thus, it is related to resilience to drought and biomass production.	Water quality, regulation and storage
16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing	Information on the abundance and composition of the soil bacterial community (α -diversity and β -diversity). Allows to assess the effects of SOC storage and CFPs on the soil microbial community.	Habitat of soil biodiversity

1.2 Objectives

This deliverable aims to provide LILAS4SOILS living lab coordinators with guidelines for selecting the soil sampling design more adequate to the characteristics of the project area (i.e., each farm or demo site at the living labs) and to collect soil data with the following objectives:

- 1) to provide a robust estimate of the spatial mean SOC stock at each demo site in the beginning of the carbon farming project.
- 2) to estimate temporal changes on SOC stocks at farm scale caused by the implementation of CFPs with a measure-and-remeasure approach, as well as with the ARMOSA process-based model (Perego et al., 2013).
- 3) to assess the effects of CFPs implemented in agricultural and agroforestry systems on several soil health indicators and related soil functions.

The end-users of this protocol are LILAS4SOILS living lab coordinators and team, and more broadly the soil science and agricultural science community involved in carbon farming projects and SOC MRV companies that want to account for effects on soil health. The deliverable begins with a short introduction on some common aspects of carbon farming MRV, continues with a theoretical overview of popular spatial sampling approaches (Section 2), it includes practical specifications of sampling design for LILAS4SOILS (Section 3.2), field and laboratory protocols to measure several soil properties during the course of the CF project (Section 3.4 and Section 3.5), to assess the effects of CFPs on SOC stocks and several indicators of soil health, soil functions or threats to soil (Evangelista et al., 2023; Lehmann et al., 2020; Liptzin et al., 2022) (Section 4). A single soil sampling design will not be suitable across all sites due to inherent differences between agricultural systems (e.g., cropland, pastures, vineyards, *montado* or *dehesa*, olive groves, etc.), degree of spatial variability in soil properties, relief, and management history within the farms, and the type of CFPs implemented at each site. Considering the technical and financial constraints of any project, we propose a simplified protocol that will allow to estimate temporal changes on SOC stocks at farm scale caused by the implementation of CFPs while providing a robust estimator of the spatial mean SOC stock.

Several soil sampling approaches require previous information on the spatial distribution of SOC content and its uncertainty at the farm level (De Gruijter et al., 2016) or environmental covariates, proxies of the soil-forming factors that influence SOC storage (Minasny and McBratney, 2006). In section 2 we provide a quick overview of the two main sampling approaches, design-based and model-based. Briefly, model-based approaches are more suitable for mapping a soil property, whereas design-based approaches are often preferred for estimating the mean or the total of a soil property for a study area. For example, with a geostatistical model we may map and predict the concentration of heavy metals at unsampled locations, whereas with design-based sampling we can calculate an unbiased estimate of the average concentration of heavy metals in the region, independently of their spatial distribution. There are multiple examples from national to local scale concerning model-based approaches for mapping SOC and soil inorganic carbon (SIC) that allow to calculate average or total SOC stocks from the predictions at every pixel (Chartin et al., 2017), whereas design-based approaches have been used to calculate unbiased estimates of SOC and SIC stocks or soil organic matter properties (Delahaie et al., 2022; Marchant et al., 2015). This protocol aims to find a trade-off between sampling effort and statistical power while providing a design-based unbiased estimator of the variance of the mean SOC change (Arrouays et al., 2018).

The sampling protocol has the objective of providing an unbiased estimate of the average temporal change in SOC stock at a demo site. The first sampling campaign (Year 0) will set the baseline SOC stock per demo site at each living lab (LL) prior the implementation of the CFPs. The sampling strategy should be able to

estimate changes in SOC stock efficiently in the subsequent sampling times and to capture the spatial variability of the SOC stock in the intervention area. Thus, the preferred sampling protocol needs to be:

- Design-based, so we obtain a valid and unbiased estimate of the change in SOC stock with associated uncertainty.
- Cost-effective, minimizing the number of samples analysed at the lab while providing reliable estimates of SOC stocks and SOC stock change at a desired confidence level.
- Easy to implement by the fieldwork team with the available resources of time and people.

Finally, the third objective is to assess the potential synergies and trade-offs between increased SOC storage associated to CFPs and soil functions. To this end, we will apply correlation analysis to the set of soil health indicators, and examine the influence of environmental conditions (climate and relief) and type of crop system on these relationships.

1.3 Definition of terms used through the protocol

For clarity we provide some definitions of the terms used throughout this protocol.

Demo site: The farm or exploitation where the CFPs will be implemented and the change in SOC stock monitored, modelled, and validated over the life of the carbon farming project. The demo site indicates the general location of the project. Despite being defined as “demo sites”, most are real farms, while few are controlled experiments by the research institutes at each living lab.

Intervention area: The specific area within the farm where the CFPs will be implemented and monitored. This area should have between 1 to 5 ha.

Sampling unit: Soil can be considered a continuum population that varies over space. Thus, the elementary sampling unit needs to be defined (Brus, 2022). Sampling units can be points (e.g., individual soil cores), or plots of different shape (e.g., rectangular or circular plots). In this sampling protocol, the sampling unit has the spatial support of a circular plot of 4 m radius (section 3). However, in the specific case of orchards, and agroforestry systems structured in alleys, transects can be the elementary sampling unit. In the context of LILAS4SOILS we prioritise having the same spatial support across all sites from different living labs as much as possible.

Sampling points: The exact locations where individual soil samples are taken within the sampling units. The scheme of sampling points within the sampling unit is explained in detail in section 3.4.2.

Soil sample: This term can be used in two instances. It refers to the individual soil samples taken at sampling points, whether they are combined to make a composite sample, or kept as an individual soil samples (e.g., for measuring bulk density and coarse fragments). It also refers to the aliquot of the bulk sample used for a laboratory analysis.

Composite sample: At each sampling unit, several individual samples are combined into a composite sample to capture the short range spatial variability in soil properties. The composite can be prepared from samples taken in transects or at circular plots.

1.4 Target spatial scale

The spatial extent of the study areas monitored by this protocol, or intervention areas (FAO, 2020), occupy between 1-5 ha. These intervention areas can correspond to a whole parcel or a section of a farm, since

the sizes of the farms participating in LILAS4SOILS range between one hectare to several hundred hectares. At the date of publication of this protocol we had information available on 47 preselected farmers. The average farm size and standard deviation was 146 ha \pm 230 ha, whereas the surface of the intervention area was 3.0 ha \pm 1.6 ha. The land cover classes following Corine Land Cover definitions (European Environmental Agency, 2019) range between arable land, pastures, perennial crops (including orchards, olive groves, vineyards) and heterogenous agricultural areas (including agro-forestry areas like dehesa or montado systems). The proportion of farms occupied by broad land cover classes was 54% to arable land, 33% to permanent crops, and 13% to grasslands.

At this spatial scale (1-5 ha) climatic conditions are likely homogeneous, although microclimatic conditions can differ due to local relief variations. Soils can be very heterogenous spatially even at farm scale. Hence, while pedoclimatic conditions are expected to be relatively homogeneous within the farms, prior information on soil characteristics from detailed soil maps or acquired with remote or proximal sensing can be used to delineate different zones or strata for the purpose of sampling and monitoring (see section 2.3). The scope of monitored areas by LILAS4SOILS is one intervention area where one or several CFPs are implemented.

A factor that will influence the choice of the sampling approach is whether the intervention area will be subject to a single or different management plans. If different combinations of CFPs are implemented within a farm (e.g., no-till and cover crops, conversion from arable to grassland), these differences in management require to be treated as different intervention areas or as different strata for planning the soil sampling and assessing the effects of different CPFs.

The methods for spatial sampling described in section 2 are applicable to larger farms and to several intervention areas, not necessarily spatially contiguous but in proximity (local scale), that can be grouped into a single carbon farming project. The latter approach is used by many companies working on SOC monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) projects (e.g., Agricarbon, SEQANA) as means to increase the cost efficiency of the soil sampling.

1.5 Minimum detectable difference and number of samples

To estimate the minimum detectable difference (MDD) in SOC stock for an acceptable level of uncertainty, we need measurements from two different times, t_0 and t_1 (FAO, 2020). To calculate the number of samples needed to achieve the desired MDD on SOC stock without available data for our study site, some authors recommend using values from the literature on the expected rate in SOC change associated with CFPs. Power analysis for a given confidence level can be applied to estimate the MDD:

$$MDD \geq \frac{S}{\sqrt{n}} (t_{\alpha,v} + t_{\beta,v})$$

where S is the standard deviation of paired differences in SOC stocks measured at t_0 and t_1 , n is the number of samples, $t_{\alpha,v}$ is the two-sided critical value of the t-distribution at a given significance level (α) (often 5 to 10 %) for v degrees of freedom ($v = n - 1$), and $t_{\beta,v}$ is the one-sided quartile of the t-distribution corresponding to a probability of type II error β (being $1 - \beta$ the statistical power, often 80 to 90%) (FAO, 2020). Then, the minimum number of samples for a desired MDD would be:

$$n \geq \left(\frac{S (t_{\alpha,v} + t_{\beta,v})}{MDD} \right)^2$$

As an example, for a confidence level of 5 % and 2 degrees of freedom, $t_{0.025,2}$ (two-tailed, $\alpha = 0.05$) is approximately 4.303. The $t_{0.2,2}$ (one-tailed, statistical power of 80%) is approximately 0.816 for 2 degrees of freedom. For a hypothetical MDD of 2 Mg C ha⁻¹ between t_0 and t_1 , and a standard deviation of paired differences in SOC stock of 1.5 Mg C ha⁻¹, the minimum number of samples would be 14.7. The sample size needs to be rounded to an integer, resulting on at least 15 soil samples.

Smaller values of MDD increase the minimum number of samples, whereas reducing the variance of the paired differences in SOC stocks would reduce the number minimum soil samples. FAO (2020) suggests carrying a preliminary sampling (5-10 samples) of the area of interest to estimate the spatial variability at farm scale, of the mean SOC. This is not the same as temporal variability but can give insight on the number of samples needed to capture the farm variability.

1.6 Space-time sampling designs

Space-time sampling design needs to define the design with respect to the two dimensions, which results on several types of sampling design classified and explained by Brus (2022) and De Gruijter et al. (2006). When our main monitoring focus is to estimate changes over the temporal dimension, the question is how the sampling units are selected for the different sampling campaigns. The sampling designs are defined as:

- **Static-synchronous (SS)**. The same sampling units are revisited in consecutive sampling campaigns.
- **Independent synchronous (IS)**. A different probability sample is selected independently at each survey.
- **Serially alternating (SA)**. Is a compromise between SS and IS. The sampling locations from the first survey are revisited at a later survey separated a determined time period, a multiple of the sampling interval (e.g., every 12 years for a sampling interval of 2 years, the period of revisits would be 6). Meanwhile, an independent sample is selected at the second survey which will be revisited after the same period, and so on. The sampling locations are revisited in the same order.
- **Supplemented panel (SP)**. Another hybrid approach, only a subset of locations from the first survey is revisited at the subsequent surveys (permanent locations). The permanent locations are supplemented with an independent sample every survey.
- **Rotating panel (RP)**. A proportion of the locations from the first survey (panel a) is revisited at the second survey and supplemented with additional locations (panel b). At the third survey, the locations that were only sampled at the previous time (panel b) are revisited and supplemented with a new sample (panel c). The same panel of locations is only sampled two consecutive times but replaced consecutively.

Depending on the persistence of the spatial pattern, Brus and De Gruijter (2013) made recommendations for choosing a space-time sampling design from a simulation study, that later Mudge et al. (2020) synthesized as follows: the SP is the best choice when there is strong persistence, whereas IS and SA are better choices for estimating the mean or the spatial trend in SOC for weak persistence of spatial patterns. In intermediate cases of moderate persistence, the choice depends on the objective of the monitoring. SS is more suitable for estimating the trend, IS is better for estimating the mean, whereas SP or SA are good choices when both parameters are of interest.

Mudge et al. (2020) summarised the advantages and disadvantages of the different designs for monitoring changes in SOC stocks in individual pastoral farms depending on if the objective of the monitoring is to estimate the mean or the trend of SOC stocks. Mudge et al. (2020) suggested that:

- Revisiting sampling locations generally improves the precision of the spatial mean estimate of change by reducing the sampling variance.
- Hence, the SS approach should reduce costs compared to IS for a required MDD in SOC. It is also simpler and easier.
- However, revising sampling locations is often avoided due to the risk of loss of market confidence out of fear of possible preferential agricultural practices near sampling locations.
- Hybrid designs like SP or SA may be better when no information on the spatial patterns of SOC are known, and we wish to estimate both the mean and trend of SOC.
- Hybrid approaches also reduce the risk of fraudulent practices since just a subset of locations are revisited and this risk is completely avoided with IS at the expense of increasing the number of required sampling locations for a desired MDC.

2. Statistical soil sampling designs

There are two main approaches that are used for monitoring soil properties over space and time, model-based and design-based. According to Brus (2021), the key differences between both approaches makes model-based approaches more appropriate for mapping, whereas design-based approaches are better when our aim is to estimate the mean or the total of a soil properties for a study area. Design-based inferences based on probability sample provide unbiased estimates and is stronger in terms of the validity of the estimate of the population mean and has a lower uncertainty for the same sample size than model-based approaches. Design-based sampling does not require assumptions about the underlying distribution of the target variable. The main difference between the two approaches is that whereas in design-based the random process needed to understand the spatial correlation originates from the random selection of sampling units (probability sampling), in model-based approaches the randomness is embedded in the statistical model of spatial variation, which is a stochastic model and therefore includes a random error term (Brus, 2014). A probability sample is therefore not needed. The validity of the estimates depends on the correctness of the assumed underlying model. There are also hybrid methods that combine the strengths of both approaches (Brus, 2021). Design-based approaches are more commonly applied for surveys and monitoring programmes, whereas model-based approaches are more commonly used for mapping or calculating estimates of the target variable in smaller areas.

Most of the sampling approaches described in this section are general designs for soil monitoring, while some of them were later applied and refined for farm-scale carbon farming auditing (e.g., OSPATS (De Gruijter et al., 2019, 2016)). There are many more types of sampling designs than those included here. For a detailed overview of sampling designs for soil survey we refer to Brus (2022) and De Gruijter et al. (2006).

2.1 Simple Random Sampling

Simple Random Sampling (SRS) is one the most basic probability sampling designs and easy to implement. The sampling can be done with and without replacement. With replacement, a population unit can be selected more than once. SRS requires little to no prior information about the spatial distribution of the soil property of interest or environmental covariates. Hence, SRS is often done at preliminary step to calculate the number of samples needed for capturing the spatial variability and estimate the mean SOC stock at a given confidence level. The disadvantage of SRS is that it is not as efficient or accurate as other designs, and as it requires a larger sample size it increases the sampling costs (Soil Survey Staff, 2025). Because no information on the soil-forming factors is used, the sample may not represent the feature space. There is also risk of generating a clustered sample that does not cover the geographical space evenly (Soil Survey Staff, 2025). Depending on the level of spatial variability, simple random sampling may lead to higher sampling variance of the mean, potentially reducing the ability to detect changes over time. This limitation can be addressed through appropriate stratification of the landscape using stratified random sampling (section 2.3). This sampling approach is not considered at LILAS4SOILS demo sites.

2.2 Area-Frame Randomized Soil Sampling

The Area-Frame Randomized Soil Sampling (AFRSS) protocol was designed by Stolbovoy et al. (2005) and updated (Stolbovoy et al., 2007) as a cost-efficient method to estimate changes in SOC stocks at croplands, pastures and forests. It does not require prior information on soil properties, relief attributes, management history, yield maps or other ancillary data. The AFRSS is a two-stage sampling design. In the first stage, a square grid of 100 cells that allows for a “modified” random sampling is overlaid with the agricultural field

or area of interest (Stolbovoy et al., 2007). The grid is numbered randomly (0-100) but avoiding that cells with consecutive numeration are too close to each other to avoid clustering of sampling units. The size of the grid is calculated from the extent of the field. The longest X or Y axis (Maxis) is divided by 10 (Grid size = $G_s = \text{Maxis}/10$) (Stolbovoy et al., 2007). The randomized sampling template is adapted to the size of the study area. Then, depending on the size of the area of interest (Table 2), n primary sampling units are selected, starting with the cell with the lowest number located completely within, and adding cells subsequently with the same criteria. This can be interpreted as that primary sampling units are selected randomly. The second phase consists of dividing each primary sampling unit into a 6 x 6 regular grid and locating 25 sampling points at the inner vertices (Figure 1). Hence, the sampling points are located at the centroid of the sampling unit and adding $G_s/6$ along N-S and E-W axes in both directions (Figure 1). Soil samples taken at the 25 points are combined into a composite, representative of the sampling unit variability. While there is a randomness component in the selection of the sampling units, this is constrained by the rule of lowest to higher numbers. The inclusion probability of all sampling units is not explicitly calculated, and thus it cannot be considered a probability sample.

Table 2: Recommended number of primary sampling units (cells of the grid) depending on the monitored area (Stolbovoy et al., 2007).

Size of the study area	Number of sampling units (n)
< 5 ha	3
5 – 10 ha	4
10 – 25 ha	5
> 25 ha	6

The AFRSS is some sort of two-stage random and systematic sampling design. The soils located near the edges of the field have higher likelihood of falling in an incomplete grid cell. Hence, these areas will be undersampled. The probability that the soils located in edge cells to be sampled is zero, thus we cannot speak of a probability sample (Brus, 2022). The sampling units can be interpreted as a finite set of adjacent squares that replace the infinite population of soil samples. There is no design-unbiased estimator of the sampling variance with this type of designs (Brus, 2022). The number of samples per sampling unit ($n = 25$) generally captures well the variability of SOC within the sampling unit. The size of the sampling unit (grid size) is scalable with the size of the study area. This can be seen as a disadvantage when applied across different demo sites because the spatial support of the sample will differ across sites. This approach has been applied to estimate changes in SOC stocks along chronosequences from agricultural lands, abandoned agricultural lands and forests (Bell et al., 2021), and to characterise the conservation of soil resources at agroecosystems at risk of desertification (Boschetto et al., 2010).

Figure 1: Sampling units selected with the Area-Frame Randomized Soil Sampling protocol for a pasture of 2.7 ha located at Behialde (Bizkaia). The selected grid cells (sampling units) are highlighted in orange, and the 25 sampling points to make a composite in black.

Compared to other sampling protocols that require between 5 to 11, the 25 samples per composite increase the time required for sampling a single demo site. The comparison of mean SOC stocks calculated with composite samples made of 25, 13, or 12 aliquots per composite applying the AFRSS protocol (Stolbovoy et al., 2007) at three sites at the Basque Country (cropland, pasture, and forest) did not find significant differences between estimates of the mean SOC stocks (unpublished data). Thus, the Stolbovoy protocol can be simplified by reducing the number of soil cores (sampling points) used to make a composite sample from 25 to 13. In the context of LILAS4SOILS we prioritise having the same area for soil sampling units (same sample support), and hence the simplified Stolbovoy will not be used, but it can be of interest for other carbon farming projects.

2.3 Stratification with clusters defined from environmental covariates

Stratification is used in soil monitoring to improve the precision of design-based estimates. **Stratification can reduce the sampling variance** because the soil samples are taken from homogeneous areas under the assumption of similar SOC range within each stratum, while capturing better the spatial variation of SOC across the monitored area. This sampling approach is recommended for LILAS4SOILS demo sites.

The inherent *capacity* of a soil to store SOC (or inherent potential) is determined and limited by the soil-forming factors (climate, organisms, relief, parent material and time (Dokuchaev, 1883; Jenny, 1941)) and intrinsic soil properties like particle size distribution, mineralogy or soil type (Georgiou et al., 2022; Lützwow et al., 2006). The current SOC storage (or current *condition* for storage of SOC) is influenced by land use and management history, land cover and vegetation, and hence is responsive to changes in management. Spatial ancillary data or environmental covariates that inform directly or indirectly on these factors can be used to stratify the area of interest into zones that are likely to exhibit differences in current SOC storage or where we expect different responses to management and CFPs. The strata can be delineated combining

information on the spatial distribution of SOC content and its uncertainty at the farm (e.g., high-resolution maps of SOC and associated uncertainty, De Gruijter et al. (2016) or environmental covariates, proxies of the soil-forming factors that influence SOC storage (Wiesmeier et al., 2019; Xia et al., 2022). At local scale, the main drivers of SOC storage are relief, soil texture and physico-chemical properties, soil microorganisms and soil fauna, land use and management (Wiesmeier et al., 2019). The proxies that are often used for stratification can include high-resolution maps of soil particle size distribution or soil texture, soil type, surface geochemistry, digital elevation models and derivative variables (e.g., slope, curvature, topographic wetness index, etc.), indicators of management intensity and history (e.g., time-series of vegetation indices like normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), yield maps, management areas). These environmental covariates or ancillary data are often available from public remote sensing databases (e.g., LANDSAT, Copernicus Sentinels) or high-resolution digital soil maps (e.g., Samarinas et al. (2023); Urbina-Salazar et al. (2023)). Electromagnetic and gamma radiometrics at high-resolution (proximal or remote sensing) are also very valuable for informing indirectly on soil properties and surface mineralogy and geochemistry (Silvero et al., 2023). There are several freely-available digital elevation models available for Europe and the Globe, e.g., Copernicus DEM at 90 m and 30 m (European Space Agency, 2022), and at 10 m for 39 countries (EEA-10 DEM), the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) at 90 m or 30 m (Earth Resources Observation And Science Centre, 2017), or the ALOS World 3D by the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA, 2024).

Long-term series of satellite imagery are very rich in information for characterising land use and land cover changes, vegetation vigour and phenology, and proxies of productivity (e.g., NDVI). Spectral bands acquired from bare soil pixels can inform directly or indirectly on soil properties related to SOC storage and soil properties that control it (Cui et al., 2025; Loiseau et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2024). This limits their application to arable land that have bare soils some time of the year or semi-arid areas with sparse vegetation (Roberts et al., 2019). Spectral indices that inform of soil properties cannot be calculated for permanent grasslands, croplands with cover crops or without periods of fallow, or with tree cover (e.g., agroforestry, orchards). Vegetation indices calculated from remote sensing time series can be used instead in these cases. Some indices that inform on soil properties (mineralogy, texture, SOC) among many others are shown in

Table 3. Moreover, a map of predictions of SOC concentration of SOC stocks can be used as input variable for stratification with clustering (Bettigole et al., 2023). For a very comprehensive and thorough review of 471 spectral indices used for soil monitoring, their definitions, limitations, and recommendations of use, we recommend the recent publication by Chen et al. (2025).

Table 3: Spectral indices calculated with Sentinel-2 spectral bands acquired on bare soils that can be potentially used for stratification. Selection of indices found in Loiseau et al. (2019) and Cui et al. (2025).

Spectral index	Expression	Related soil properties	References
Coloration index	$(\text{Red}-\text{Green})/(\text{Red}+\text{Green})$	Soil color	(Ray et al., 2004)
Grain size index	$(\text{Red}-\text{Blue})/(\text{Red}+\text{Green}+\text{Blue})$	Fine sand content	(Xiao et al., 2006)
Clay index	SWIR1/SWIR2	Clay	(Joint Research Centre, Hengl, 2007)
Redness Index	$\text{Red}^2/(\text{Blue}*\text{Green}^3)$	Hematite content	(Ray et al., 2004)
Carbonate Index	Red/Green	Carbonate	(Amen and Blaszczyński, 2001)
Ferrous Iron	Red/SWIR1	Ferrous iron	(Amen and Blaszczyński, 2001)

Normalised difference Geological response	$(SWIR1-SWIR2)/(SWIR1+SWIR2)$	Geological response (gypsum, silt)	(Niield et al., 2007)
Normalised difference Calcareous sediments	$(SWIR1-Green)/(SWIR1+Green)$	Calcareous Sedimentary rocks	(Niield et al., 2007)
SOC Index	$Blue/(Green \times Red)$	Soil Organic Carbon	(Zhu et al., 2024)
Gypsum Index	$(SWIR1-NIR)/(SWIR2+NIR)$	Gypsum	(Wang et al., 2022)
SWIR/NIR Carbon Index	$SWIR2/NIR$	Soil carbon	(Zhu et al., 2024)

The strata can be used as basis for stratified random sampling to make several composites, or to locate first-order sparse measurement points (as explained more in detail in section 2.4). This method of stratification is suggested by many soil carbon MRV protocols like the FAO-GSCOC (2020) or VM0042 (Verra, 2024). When the objective is to assess the temporal change in SOC stock it is a good option to maintain the same stratification in subsequent years.

The number of strata and the minimum number of samples recommended by stratum vary among protocols, and it is related to the heterogeneity of the terrain to be sampled, the available budget and the desired precision. FAO-GSCOC (2020) recommends creating a minimum of 3 strata and from 5 to 10 sampling locations per stratum. Creating composite samples is allowed to reduce laboratory costs, but maintaining a minimum of 3 composites per stratum. Other protocols do not specify a minimum number of strata or samples per stratum, although they suggest calculating the minimum number of samples needed to detect a statistically significant MDD for a given confidence level. The optimal number of clusters (strata) when applying unsupervised classification with clustering algorithms (e.g. k-means) is often selected using internal clustering quality indices like the Silhouette (Rousseeuw, 1987), Calinski-Harabasz (Calinski and Harabasz, 1974) or Dunn (Dunn, 1974) indices among many others.

We stratified the pasture at Behialde using as covariates elevation, slope, the product of northness by slope (a proxy for exposure), topographic wetness index (TWI), and NDVI (standard deviation and the median from each quarter of the year) (Figure 2). The NDVI was calculated from the Harmonized Sentinel-2 MSI (MultiSpectral Instrument, Level-2A (SR)) image collection at 10 m resolution. Processing the Sentinel-2 time series was performed with Google Earth Engine. The date of acquisition of the images ranged from 01/01/2018 to 31/12/2024, and selected images had less than 20% clouds. Clouds and cirrus pixels were masked prior calculating NDVI for each image. Then, the median of NDVI for the first (January-March), second (April-June), third (July-September) and fourth (October-December) quarters and the standard deviation of the whole time series were calculated.

Figure 2: Covariates used for stratification using environmental covariates.

We standardised all variables (mean centred and scaled) and decorrelated the data with the Cholesky transformation (Wicklin, 2012). The latter step allows to use the Mahalanobis distance for k-means clustering, since several covariates are highly correlated (e.g., elevation and TWI, or NDVI variables). The optimal number of strata was examined with the Dunn, Calinski-Harabasz and Silhouette indices. Whereas the Dunn index proposed 2 as optimal number of strata, Silhouette and Calinski-Harabasz suggested 6 strata. The final k-means models were created with k-means clustering selecting the best of 10 initializations and k-means ++ initialization method. We generated maps for 2, 3 and 6 strata (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Stratification of Behalde pasture using environmental covariates for 2, 3 and 6 strata.

The map of 6 strata differentiates the areas near the study area boundaries, probably due to the spectral signal influenced by the dirt road and the trees (see strata numbers 4 and 5). Based on visualization of the results, we could select two or three strata. According to the protocol by the FAO-GSCOC (2020), we would select 3 strata, with an area occupied by each of them varying considerably (stratum 1 = 19 %, stratum 2 = 72 %, stratum 3 = 9%). We stress that at least two sampling units should be allocated by stratum to be able to calculate the sampling variance per stratum (see equation 12 in section 4), hence a minimum of six sampling units would be needed at Behialde. It may be the case that due to budget limitations the total number of sampling units does not allow that, e.g., maximum of three sampling units/farm, as is the case for LILAS4SOILS. Hence, if we selected two strata, given that stratum 1 covers 67% of the field and stratum 2 occupies 33%, we could assign three samples proportionally to the area (two samples in stratum 1, and one sample in stratum 2) (Figure 4.a).

Figure 4: Stratified random sampling with allocation proportional to stratum area for Behialde. a) All sampling points fall within the field boundaries, b) One sampling point was assigned at a pixel that had part of its area outside the boundaries of the intervention area.

2.4 Stratification with compact geographical strata

Stratifying can help improving the precision of design-based estimates. However, when there is no prior information available on the variability of the soil properties, SOC stocks, management history or other environmental factors that influence SOC storage for applying the method of section 2.3, stratifying considering the space is a good option. Sampling designs with compact geographical strata are advantageous when no ancillary data on SOC storage is available (Chappell et al., 2013; De Gruijter et al., 2006; Guerrero and Lorenzetti, 2021), or there is no possibility to explore other stratifications (e.g., lack of time or expertise for exploring stratification with proxies of yield, management history, relief, etc.), or when the area of interest is relatively homogeneous. The main advantage is that as we take a probability sample, **the sample mean is an unbiased estimator of the population mean (mean SOC), and we also obtain an unbiased estimate of the sampling variance of the mean change in SOC**. In the context of LILAS4SOILS this method is applied to study areas of 1-5 ha, but it can also be applied for soil monitoring at local or regional scale, increasing the number of compact strata and number of sampling units per stratum.

The study area (field, pasture, permanent crop, etc.) is divided into strata that are geographically compact (i.e., strata are defined from the pixel coordinates, as groups of adjacent pixels) and of relatively equal size. Strata of the same size have the advantage that their weights are the same, and the estimate of the sample mean is an unbiased estimator of the population mean (Brus, 2022). Stratification based on geographical strata improves the spatial coverage of the sample. The user can define the number of pixels in which the study area is divided. Once the strata are defined, the sampling design for collecting the samples within each stratum can vary among multiple methods. The compact geographical strata can be generated with the R package *spsosa* (Walvoort et al., 2023). At least 2 samples are needed per stratum to be able to compute sampling variance.

2.4.1 Stratified simple random sampling using compact geographical strata

A selection of a random sample from each stratum can be done with different designs. An example is the simple random sample (

Figure 5.a). However, we can set up a sampling unit as in a two-stage sampling design. The location of the random points can be used as the centre of the sampling unit. Within these sampling units we can collect samples at secondary sampling points for making a composite. This sampling approach is considered for LILAS4SOILS demo sites.

Arrouays et al. (2018) designed a sampling protocol for monitoring SOC stock changes for the Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS) testing it at 9 CarboEurope sites (<https://www.carboeurope.org/>) using a two-stage stratified random sampling. They used geographically compact sub-areas as strata to avoid clustering the sampling locations and to improve the accuracy of the spatial mean SOC stock. This sampling approach is a probability sample, which allows to estimate the statistical parameters efficiently with a small sample size (Arrouays et al., 2018). They created 20 strata of equal area and at each stratum they located two circular plots of 10 m radius. These circular plots are the first-order sparse measurement points. Within each circular plot, they assigned 5 locations randomly, that are the second-order sparse measurement points, and that were combined into a composite sample.

We illustrate a modified version of the protocol by Arrouays et al. (2018) at Behialde (

Figure 5) defining three compact strata, two plots per stratum, and 10 secondary random sampling points per circular plot. In this example, the number of strata is three because this is the minimum required by some established protocols (e.g., FAO). The number of secondary random sampling points is arbitrary (e.g.,

it could be 5 random sampling points). Alternatively, the second-order sampling points could be located at predetermined locations from the first-order measuring point (e.g., as in LUCAS, or the approach proposed for LILAS4SOILS in section 3.4.2). In the case of LILAS4SOILS, it may not be possible to carry the two-stage stratified random sampling, but a single sampling unit would be allocated per stratum.

a)

b)

Figure 5: Two-stage stratified random sampling from geographical compact strata. a) The first stage consists in dividing the area of interest into equal-area compact strata and selecting two samples per stratum randomly. b) The second stage consists of delineating plots of 10 m radius around the locations and selecting randomly 10 points per plot. The area of interest is a pasture at Behialde (Bizkaia, Spain).

2.4.2 Stratified simple random sampling for composite samples

Simple random sampling can be applied within each stratum. The same number of samples are assigned per stratum since they are equal-area strata. If there are no budget constraints, we can analyse each sample individually. However, to reduce the laboratory costs we can create composite samples combining several samples in one composite sample from each stratum. By increasing the number of strata, we improve the spatial coverage, avoid that points are spatially clustered and likely obtain a good spatial estimate of the mean SOC stock for the area of interest. As an example, we illustrate a stratified simple random sampling at the pasture of Behialde creating 15 strata and making 3 composites from a total of 45 individual soil samples (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Stratified random sampling from geographical compact strata for preparing composite samples. The area of interest is a pasture at Behialde (Bizkaia, Spain).

2.5 Targeted sampling

This sampling approach is attractive for systems where we expect clear differences in soil properties due to management strategies (e.g., crop alleys and agroforestry) and is often used in precision agriculture for sampling soils and crop attributes. The FAO protocol (FAO, 2020) and several references in the literature refer to directed stratified sampling, targeted sampling, or zonal sampling to the approach that we define here as stratification with clusters defined from environmental covariates (section 2.3). We prefer the term “stratification with clusters defined from environmental covariates” to emphasize the underlying randomness in the selection of the sampling points, i.e., probability sampling. On the other hand, the term “targeted sampling” may be more suitable when the purpose of the sampling is to identify areas where some soil properties might be above or below critical levels, e.g., high concentration of pollutants or salinity.

For specific agroecosystems like agroforestry or orchards, Dehesa and montado, targeted sampling can refer to locations with relative distances of trees where we can expect much higher SOC stocks compared to arable areas (Cardinael et al., 2017; Minarsch et al., 2024). Targeted sampling can use high resolution imagery or remote sensing data (aerial photographs, electromagnetic induction maps, management maps, etc.) for identifying zones (strata) with presumed differences on SOC levels. For instance, very high-resolution remote sensing data can be applied to map individual tree crowns with supervised deep-learning and machine learning algorithms in agroforestry systems or open forests (Brandt et al., 2020; Skole et al., 2021), as a preliminary step for sampling design, separating areas under and outside the canopies into different strata. In the case of lacking very high-resolution remote sensing data, a sketch of the different zones and general tree spacing at the site can be prepared during fieldwork at agroforestry or alley orchard systems.

Dehesa and montado systems have large spatial variation within and among exploitations, mainly due to tree density, distribution, age and crown size along with the relief and inherent soil heterogeneity (e.g., stoniness and soil depth, clay content and mineralogy). Farm management also has a significant impact on these systems. Tree (e.g., trees pruning and use of residues; cork harvest sections across the exploitation)

and livestock (e.g., cattle species, load intensity and grazing) management is especially relevant in this regard. Other farm operations related to soils coverage (e.g. pasture/crops permanence and diversity or bushes presence) and tillage practices (e.g., frequency, timing, depth, rationale) must be also considered.

Three separate cases will be considered for the demo sites at LILAS4SOILS, crop alley systems (section 3.2.3), dehesa/montado (section 3.2.4), and terraced systems (section 3.2.5).

2.6 Conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling

Conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling (cLHS) was adapted by Minasny and McBratney (2006) from the classic Latin Hypercube sampling algorithm to soil mapping and monitoring. This sampling approach does not obtain probability samples, and hence it is not possible to obtain an unbiased estimate. This sampling approach has become very popular and very often it outperforms other stratification methods like k-means on environmental covariates or SOC predictions (Bettigole et al., 2023). cLHS optimizes the coverage of the covariate space (covariate space is the multivariate combination of the different environmental covariates within the study area). The domain of each covariate is divided into n equal sized marginal strata, where n is also the sample size. For p covariates, this results in p^n marginal strata. The bounds of the marginal strata are selected with quantiles from the evenly spaced cumulative probabilities so that the number of grid cells in each stratum is equal. An example of its application in Behialde for a sample size of 6 units is shown in Figure 7. The covariates were the same as in section 2.4 (elevation, slope, product of northness by slope, TWI, and NDVI).

The objective function of Minasny and McBratney (2006) has the following criteria (Malone et al., 2019):

- Matching the sample with the empirical distribution functions of the continuous ancillary variables;
- Matching the sample with the empirical distribution functions of the categorical ancillary variables; and
- Matching the sample with the correlation matrix of the continuous ancillary variables.

The cLHS has been modified to account for inaccessibility to the original sampling locations, supplement an existing dataset, or optimizing sample size (Malone et al., 2019).

Figure 7: Conditional Latin Hypercube Sampling for six sampling points at Behialde.

2.7 OSPATS+

De Gruijter et al. (2016b) developed a sophisticated methodology for measuring and auditing changes in SOC stocks at farm level building from a stratification method that uses digital soil mapping (DSM) products (a map of predictions of SOC stocks and their uncertainties) to define strata (OSPATS) (De Gruijter et al., 2015). Their methodology applies a design-based approach, with stratified simple random sampling and optimal allocation of samples to strata that minimizes the sampling variance of the mean (Neyman allocation, see section 2.8). Some decisions regarding the sampling strategy are that the sampled locations differ between the initial and subsequent sampling times to reduce the risk of fraudulent practices, the SOC stock is measured directly on whole soil cores, and the soil samples are not bulked (De Gruijter et al., 2016a). The area of the farm is discretised into a fine grid, and each cell is treated as a sampling unit. The objective function is minimized by iterative re-allocation, defined with generalized distances between pairs of grid points, calculated by the difference between the predictions, the variances of the prediction errors and their covariance. The optimization criterion to select the total sample size is based on the value of information, prioritising the expected profit for the farmer (carbon credits), accounting for the added value of the samples reducing the uncertainty of the mean change in SOC and the cost of data collection, for a given level of certainty about the sequestered carbon. The information from the first sampling campaign is used to improve the predictions of the SOC map and reducing its associated uncertainty, hence reducing the final variance of the difference in mean SOC stock. There is software available for applying the stratification algorithm OSPATS in with scripts for R (Malone and Saby, 2019), the function *optimizeStrataSpatial* in the R package *SamplingStrata* (Ballin and Barcaroli, 2020) and OSPATS+ is available as a package for the programming language Julia to increase the computation speed (De Gruijter et al., 2019).

2.8 Allocation of soil samples among strata

There are several methods frequently used in the literature for assigning the number of samples among strata that Bettigole et al. (2023) summarized as follows:

- Even. The same number of samples are allocated to each stratum.
- Area-weighted sample. The number of samples are proportional to the area occupied by each stratum. If the total area of the monitoring area is A , given a total number of samples for our intervention area n , and A_h the area of stratum h , then the number of samples in that stratum, n_h is calculated as follows. The number of samples is rounded to integers.

$$n_h = n \frac{A_h}{\sum A_h} \quad [1]$$

- Neyman allocation. Neyman allocation optimizes the samples allocated to each stratum (n_s) based on the total number of samples (n), mean covariate values per strata (x_s), mean covariate across all strata (x), within-strata standard deviation of covariates (σ_s), and standard deviation across all strata (σ). Instead of environmental covariates, we can apply Neyman allocation on maps of SOC stocks or concentration.

$$n_s = n \frac{x_s \cdot \sigma_s}{x \cdot \sigma} \quad [2]$$

- Bethel algorithm. Bethel (1989) defined a method to determine the optimal total sample size and the allocation of sampling units across strata, accounting for a desired precision level of the estimates (coefficient of variation) and minimising a cost function. It can be applied to univariate or multivariate survey. Bethel's algorithm uses lagrangian multipliers to find the minimum sample size for a given stratification that fulfils the required precision. Ballin and Barcaroli (2013) later developed a method to define the stratification, total sample size and sample allocation jointly using the genetic algorithm and estimating the cost of associated sample with the Bethel algorithm. Bethel's algorithm can be applied in R with the package *SamplingStrata* (Barcaroli, 2014).
- Mean bias-weighted sampling. This method assigns samples with weights based on the average distance from the stratum mean SOC (or SOC observations at a stratum h , z_h) to the mean SOC at the study site (\hat{z}). The method can use laboratory measurements of SOC at the site or high-resolution spatial predictions on SOC.

$$n_h = \log \left(\frac{\sum |z_h - \hat{z}|}{z_h} \right) \quad [3]$$

Bettigole et al. (2023) recommended to avoid even allocation and creating at least 5 strata based on ancillary data for farms of area ranging between 60-230 ha.

2.9 Choice of sampling design

The inherent spatial variability of soil properties and pedogenetic conditions influencing SOC storage within a study site, the availability of SOC data, the spatial scale of the SOC monitoring project, and the availability of resources will determine our choice of sampling design (VandenBygaart, 2006). Lawrence et al. (2020) provided several questions to guide the decision of the optimal sampling approach for surveying soil properties depending on the monitoring objective, the spatial autocorrelation, the extent and scale of management within the field, availability of ancillary data and resources. Previously, Brus and De Gruijter (1997) gave several criteria for choosing between sampling approaches, including the type of request, need

for objectivity, need of estimation variance at all points or subregions, the interest in valid and accurate estimates of the estimation or prediction variance, the quality of the model, the autocorrelation between observation and prediction points, and the sample size. We provide a simpler decision tree to guide the choice of spatial sampling approach in the context of LILAS4SOILS (Figure 8). Most SOC MRV protocols require stratification, so we have highlighted stratification based on compact geographical strata and stratification based on environmental covariates. These two methods can be combined with more systematic approaches for targeted sampling at agroforestry or silvopastoral systems.

There are multiple studies comparing different sampling designs in terms of efficiency and accuracy for estimating change in SOC stocks (Bettigole et al., 2023; Bradford et al., 2023; Potash et al., 2023). Sampling designs that incorporate information on environmental covariates, remote sensing, soil type and spatial predictions of SOC generally improve sample efficiency in comparison to SRS, but which sampling design is better seems to be site-dependent (Bettigole et al., 2023; Potash et al., 2023) making the generalization of the best sampling approach difficult across study areas, e.g., Bettigole et al. (2023) recommend cLHS whereas Potash et al. (2023) prefer doubly balance sampling.

The required sampling density is generally higher when the purpose of the study is mapping than when it is estimating population parameters. For mapping at field scale up to several hectares, Žižala et al. (2024) suggested that between 18 to 30 samples ($0.6 - 1 \text{ sample ha}^{-1}$) could suffice for sampling with covariate-informed approaches (e.g., cLHS or Feature Space Coverage Sampling (FSCS)). Notice that while cLHS is not a probability design, FSCS can provide a design-based probability sample if the location of the sampling units within the strata are selected randomly. The required sampling density also decreases as the area of the farm or carbon farming project increases, allowing for better cost efficiency (€/ha sampling) at larger projects. A common practice for improving sampling efficiency for monitoring carbon farming projects is to group several properties (farms, fields, etc.) that can be contiguous or not, into the same project. Bradford et al. (2023) found that even at high sampling densities commonly used at MRV projects (e.g., $1.2 \text{ ha sample}^{-1}$) and moderate within-field spatial variability, the estimates of SOC change for single fields were largely inaccurate. When several fields were grouped together, the estimates of change in SOC stocks gained in robustness and accuracy at higher sampling densities and larger number of fields (Bradford et al., 2023).

Finally, the support of the sampling units can vary greatly between sampling protocols in size and shape, from points (e.g., a soil core) to squares or circular plots. The soil samples can be individual or composite, with the number of samples taken within a soil monitoring unit for preparing composites varying as well among existing protocols. While several studies suggest that increasing the number of samples bulked into a composite over five does not provide significant advantages, other protocols require a larger number of samples (ranging from 10 to 25) for capturing the SOC variability within the monitoring unit (Stolbovoy et al., 2007). As a compromise between these alternatives, the common protocol for LILAS4SOILS proposed in this document takes 9 samples for preparing a composite sample per monitoring unit (see section 3.4.2).

Figure 8: Simplified decision tree for selection of spatial sampling approach.

3. Protocols for soil sampling and laboratory analyses

There is not a single recipe for finding the best protocol across sites. Rather than suggesting a single sampling design, this document provides guidelines for selection of the approach that will be best suited to each demo site and living lab. However, the preference is 1) stratification based on environmental covariates and 2) stratification from compact geostrata for croplands, pastures, and permanent crops. In the case of alley crops and dehesa/montado, each of these systems has their specific protocol.

3.1 Spatial boundaries of intervention area

The spatial delineation of the intervention area (area that will be used for implementing CFPs and monitored for SOC changes) should exclude the roads or buildings located within its boundaries. The delineation can be done using freely available and user-friendly software like Google Earth Pro or geographic information systems (GIS) software (ArcGIS, QGIS) with the support of the most updated satellite imagery.

The Coordinate Reference System (CRS) used when delineating the boundaries should be the most widely used in the region of study and suitable for doing the field sampling (the same as in the GPS device), but it is not strictly necessary at this stage. However, it is important to know and record the CRS (geodetic datum and coordinate system, or EPSG code). For example, OpenStreet Map and Google Maps use EPSG: 3857 (Web Mercator, with World Geodetic System 1984). Once the spatial sampling has been designed and we obtain the coordinates of the sampling points, these can be **transformed into the projection of the GPS with the correct transformation**. For example, for the pasture at Behialde (Basque Country, Spain), the CRS is EPSG:25830 (datum European Terrestrial Reference System 1989, and projection UTM Zone 30N, units in meters).

3.2 Protocol for spatial sampling

Detailed maps of soil classes, when available for our area of study, should be examined to gain preliminary information about the soil type and its spatial heterogeneity in the intervention area. Information on soil classes may be used for stratification, but also for understanding the characteristics of or soil and potential response and limitations to CFPs.

3.2.1 Stratified random sampling using environmentally defined clusters as strata

When available information on environmental covariates related to SOC storage or high-resolution maps of SOC stocks and associated uncertainty (with reliable validation statistics) are available for the intervention area and the demo sites, stratification from environmentally defined clusters will be the preferred approach following the indications of section 2.3 and Annex A.

The resulting maps of strata need to be validated visually by the living lab coordinators based on their knowledge of the area and could also count with the assessment by the farmers who are the ones who know best their soils. This evaluation would answer the question *Do you think these areas are different in terms of landscape, soil properties (e.g., soil texture) and the response of crops to management practices?*

The selection of the optimal number of strata can be done with internal clustering quality indices widely used in the literature (e.g., Silhouette, Calinski-Harabasz, Dunn, etc.), preferably 2-3 strata in intervention areas of 1-5 ha. While most MRV protocols set a minimum of 3 strata, the final choice should be done with

careful evaluation of the results from the clustering exercise, since the surface of the intervention area is relatively small.

The allocation of sampling units to each stratum will be proportional to their area (section 2.8). If high-resolution and reliable maps of SOC stocks and uncertainty are the spatial layers used for stratification, Neyman allocation is also recommended.

The results of the stratification and preliminary analysis of the environmental covariates (visualization of maps, histograms, etc) may suggest that the intervention area is very homogeneous. Hence, stratification may not add valuable information for reducing the sampling variance. Sometimes, lack of time to prepare the sampling design, available data or expertise for conducting this method may limit its application. In both cases, we would select the next sampling approach, stratified random sampling from compact geostrata.

The sampling units (circular plot of 4 m radius) will be allocated with the coordinates of their centre. We start assigning the first sampling unit per stratum. If the circular plot intersects the boundary of the stratum or the monitoring area, generate a different random sample (changing the seed in the R script) until the three plots fall within the boundaries. Then, add consecutively the additional plots per stratum keeping a minimum distance between centres of the plots of 15 m (Arrouays et al., 2018). These sampling units will be resampled at the years 2 (2027) and 3 (2028) of the project LILAS4SOILS.

3.2.2 Stratified random sampling using geographically compact sub-areas as strata

At intervention areas where the soil conditions, relief, and management history are presumed to be homogeneous, environmentally defined strata may not be necessary. Stratification with compact geostrata (Brus, 2022) would then be our selected approach following the indications of section 2.3 and Annex A. The intervention area will be divided into three compact strata of equal area and a minimum of one sampling unit (circular plot of 4 m radius) will be located randomly at each stratum. We acknowledge that a minimum of two sampling units should be located within each stratum to be able to compute the sampling variance by stratum, but due to budget constraints this may not be possible at all living labs. Because the strata have the same size, this allocation is also proportional to the area of the stratum. Depending on the available resources, we might expand the number of sampling units to n , and then the number of sampling units per stratum h would be $n_h = n/3$. This would improve our spatial estimate of the mean SOC and its variance.

The sampling units (circular plot of 4 m radius) will be allocated with the coordinates of their centre. We start assigning the first sampling unit per stratum. If the circular plot intersects the boundary of the stratum or the monitoring area, generate a different random sample until the three plots fall within the boundaries. Then, add consecutively the additional plots per stratum keeping a minimum distance between centres of the plots of 15 m (Arrouays et al., 2018). These sampling units will be resampled at the years 2 (2027) and 3 (2028) of the project LILAS4SOILS. At each soil monitoring unit, we will implement the field sampling protocol.

3.2.3 Crop or agroforestry structured in alleys

Targeted sampling might be preferred by the coordinator of the carbon farming project in orchards or agroforestry systems that are structured in alleys to capture the effect of specific CFPs (e.g. hedgerows, lines of trees). We refer the reader to the systematic review and harmonised protocol by Minarsch et al. (2024). The intervention area might be stratified with environmental covariates or geostrata before assigning transect sampling units across the area to ensure that the soil variability and/or the geographical area is covered.

Minarsch et al. (2024) recommended 4 transects per alley cropping system (ACS) (i.e., equivalent to the intervention area in this protocol). In the case of LILAS4SOILS demo sites, the minimum required will be 3 transects per intervention area or ACS due to limitations of resources. The levels of tree influence shall be considered when selecting transect positions. The location of replicated transects should be systematic rather than random. The approximate area proportions of the tree and arable/pasture strips need to be registered at the field for calculations of weighted SOC stocks at the ACS area. Field records or delineation from very high-resolution aerial photographs are possible options.

Minarsch et al., (2024) proposed two types of composite sampling. The first composite sampling scheme places the transects in parallel to the tree lines, establishing seven transects: one at the tree line, then three at each side (at 1 m from the edge of the tree strip, at a quarter of the arable width, and half of the arable strip). This method of composite sampling would account for the influence of trees on SOC content and bulk density. However, it increases substantially the number of analytical samples at the laboratory. In the second type, the composites are made along a transect that covers both sides of the interrow around the tree strip, from 7 individual samples. Four transects are placed relative to tree positions: under a tree, between two trees, and at one quarter distance to the tree line. This method of composite sampling homogenises differences in SOC content in the tree rows and the interrows. However, it is difficult to account for differences in bulk density under different vegetation cover. Hence, bias in bulk density estimates will be introduced for the calculation of SOC stocks, unless several bulk density samples are taken at different distances from the trees and averaged.

Because we can expect differences in bulk density between tree lines and the interrows, we should collect separate samples from tree strips and interrows, which also calls for creating composite samples for tree lines and interrows separately. We propose to simplify the method by Minarsch et al., (2024) by creating **one composite at the tree line, a second composite in the interrow** (Figure 9). This would duplicate the number of laboratory analyses (e.g., 3 replicates x 2 transects (tree line & interrow)). The same transects will be revisited in subsequent times. The number of soil samples that would be taken at each transect for creating the composite samples will be explained more in detail in section 3.4.2 Field sampling.

Agroforestry systems like dehesas or montados where trees are spread irregularly or in clusters, or terraced systems need a spatial sampling design tailored to their specific conditions (see section 3.2.4 and section 3.2.5).

Figure 9: Modification of the composite sampling scheme proposed by Minarsch et al. (2024) for soil organic carbon monitoring in temperate alley cropping systems. The patterns for making three composite samples in parallel to the tree lines – at the tree line, at a quarter of the distance between tree lines, and half the distance between tree lines. Additional bulk density samples per transect.

3.2.4 Dehesa and montado systems

The sampling approach adapted to these systems considers two issues: a) what are the CFPs that will be implemented at dehesa/montado systems in LILAS4SOILS' demo sites? and b) which sampling approaches can detect temporal changes in SOC storage?

Most of the 19 CFPs identified by LILAS4SOILS could be potentially implemented in dehesas/montados demo sites e.g., no tillage, cover cropping, animal fertility improvement, organic farming including livestock.

The main challenge when designing a sampling approach for these systems is dealing with the large spatial variations of key features within a farm and among farms. In this regard, structural variations in tree density and distribution, crown size, and age, along with relief and soil (e.g. stoniness, depth) variations. Moreover, the management of dehesa/montados are also a source of relevant variations that need to be considered when sampling their soils. This includes the management of trees through pruning and use of residues or cork harvest, livestock in association to cattle species, load intensity and holistic grazing, soil coverage by means of pasture and/or crop permanence and species selected and presence of bushes, and tillage (frequency, period, and depths).

The suggested stratified sampling strategy considers both areas under the influence of oak trees and the areas between them and relies on very high-resolution remote sensing to identify rock outcrop areas. Presumed differences in bulk density is also a key feature to consider as affected by livestock, tillage and machinery.

Hence, the suggested sampling strategy for these agro-silvo-pastoral systems consists in the following steps: 1) when the farm has a relatively large extension and irregular relief, consider a first stratification based on relief covariates (e.g., elevation, slope or topographic wetness index) (Figure 10). This step may

not be necessary. 2) Overlay a second stratification that identifies individual tree canopies. This step can be done by manual photointerpretation or combining unsupervised classification and object-based image analysis of very-high resolution aerial photographs. 3) At each combination tree strata, select five consecutively trees and sample under the canopy of each tree in two random sampling points, and create a composite sample (composite of 8 samples) (Figure 11); similarly, sample outside the canopy between the trees taking two random samples at each segment between trees. Then, make a composite (composite of 8 samples) for the stratum “outside the tree canopy”. Since bulk density is more difficult to measure, it is proposed to measure it in two sampling points, one under one tree canopy and another outside of the canopy (Figure 11). The selection of sampling units (transects of consecutive trees) needs to have an element of randomness for it to be a probability sample. Hence, we propose that the location of the first tree where the concatenation of sampling points begins is selected randomly. The calculation of sampling variance per stratum requires at least two samples, i.e., minimum two composite samples below canopy, and two composite samples outside the canopy with a total of four sapling unit per demo site. In the case of Figure 10 that would result at a minimum of six composite samples (3 relief strata x 2 vegetation cover strata). The total number of samples can be adjusted depending on the available resources.

Figure 10: First stratification step of intervention area at a dehesa system (Salamanca, Spain) applying unsupervised classification to elevation and topographic wetness index data.

Figure 11: Scheme of sampling approach at dehesa and montado. The eight samples for each type of vegetation cover (below canopy or outside the tree canopy) are combined into their respective composite samples. There are two sampling points for bulk density, one below the canopy and a second one outside the tree canopy. Illustration by Mercedes Román Dobarco.

3.2.5 Terraced systems

Agricultural systems in steep terrain frequently use terraces, particularly common in Mediterranean vineyards and olive groves. These landscapes exhibit strong within-field heterogeneity, especially between the terrace edge (row) and inner flat areas (interrow), due to historic soil redistribution and depth variability. Terraced systems can vary greatly in geomorphology and regularity of the relief, architecture and shape, width of the flat terraced area, type of slope (gradual or vertical wall), and age of the system (from newly constructed to often several centuries old). The age of the terrace system and type of terrace influences SOC storage (Chen et al., 2020), making the selection of a sampling approach challenging. Microrelief will influence strongly the content of SOC and its spatial variation. High-resolution topographic techniques allow to have very detailed mapping of terraces, differentiating between the flat interrow areas, the rows of perennial crops, and the slopes or terrace edges (Cucchiaro et al., 2021). However, terrain attributes calculated with very high-resolution DEM, e.g., slopes, can differentiate flat and the slope areas of the terraced system, but using them for a general stratification of the demo site may obscure differences due to the parent material or inherent soil properties. A possibility is to test if the information of aspect covariates (e.g., northerness or easterness) calculated from smoothed DEM is meaningful.

Preliminary information on the specific characteristics of the terrace system, and given certain similarities with permanent crops structured in alleys or other agroforestry systems, and the type of CFPs that will be tested at the demo sites, we can consider applying sampling approaches already used in the protocol:

1. Prior stratification of the intervention area or demo site can be done using remote sensing data of vegetation or bare soil indices, geomorphology maps, proximal sensing data (e.g. electromagnetic induction) or digital soil maps of soil class or properties (e.g., particle size distribution, apparent electrical conductivity).
2. At very wide terraces or with relatively irregular terrain:
 - a. Sampling units of 4 m radius (see section 3.4.2) can be appropriate to take a probability sample and capture the short-range spatial variability in soil properties.
 - b. When wide and irregular terraces have orchards (e.g., avocado trees, olive trees), a stratified targeted sampling similar to the design for dehesa or montado can allow to differentiate areas under canopy from areas outside the canopy.
3. At narrower terrace systems, transect sampling parallel to contour lines, in a similar manner as with alley crop systems or dehesa and montado systems may be more appropriate. In this case, we have two options:
 - a. Targeted stratified sampling differentiating the interrow and the row of perennial crops.
 - b. Transect sampling at the row of perennial crops (very narrow terraces with just one line of crops).

3.2.6 What should we do if we are conducting the sampling at the field, and we find out that it is not possible to sample one of the sampling units?

- This can happen if we see the sampling unit has been strongly disturbed recently, it is crossed by a trail or an area where the machinery passes with higher frequency (e.g., turning), etc.
- We will avoid choosing by convenience the next sampling unit in the proximity of the theoretical one, because this would introduce bias (Brus, 2022).
- In the case we are using circular plots at compact geostrata or strata defined from environmental covariates, we will go to the field with a **second set of numbered sampling units** generated with a different randomization (e.g., different allocation of circular plots within the strata). The fieldwork team will have an alternate set of sampling units and have the coordinates of the centre of the plots saved at the GPS.
- The sampling unit from the first set that is not suitable for sampling will be substituted by the **first sampling unit from the alternative set for that stratum** (Brus, 2022).
- Therefore, it is imperative to bring a digital or printed map with the location of both sets of sampling plots (primary and alternative) and their coordinates.

3.2.7 Resampling

It is very important that the field team records the real coordinates of the centre of the sampling units so that **the same locations can be resampled in the next field campaigns**.

In the subsequent years we will revisit the same sampling units, although with slight variation in the location of the sub-samples for making the composite samples. The selected approach is a static synchronous sampling design, suitable for identifying the trend in SOC (De Gruijter et al., 2006). Compared to other space-time designs, the sampling variance is reduced by revisiting the sampling sites because the temporal

correlation is accounted for, hence improving the spatial mean estimate of SOC change (Mudge et al., 2020). Revisiting the sample sampling units improves the cost efficiency to detect change in SOC with a smaller number of samples. However, several authors have advised against resampling the same locations of fear that this might influence the intensity and spatial application of CFPs (Mudge et al., 2020). After finalisation of fieldwork, we should try to leave the sampling points as least disturbed as possible, filling the holes where coarse fragments and bulk density samples have been taken with the remaining soil.

3.3 Soil properties measured at different soil monitoring times

The complete set of soil properties for calculating SOC stock and additional indicators of several soil functions will be measured at Year 0 (2025), prior to the implementation of the CFPs (Table 4). The same set of soil properties (except particle size distribution) will be measured at Year 3 (2028), to assess the change in SOC stock and associated evolution of indicators of soil functions. Soil texture is considered stable over the duration of the carbon farming project and hence is measured only at Year 0. Some properties, like particle size distribution, carbonates, and total Nitrogen (TN) are used for modelling carbon dynamics with the hybrid approach for soil carbon MRV (Table 4).

At the intermediate sampling time (Year 2, 2027), we will measure the properties needed for calculating SOC stocks, i.e., bulk density, SOC content and coarse fragments. The reason to have an intermediate sampling time just for SOC stock is that the interannual variability may obscure the trend on SOC change due to the CFPs, and as a contingency measure in the case that a strong disturbance (e.g., extreme drought, wildfire) hinders the field sampling at Year 3. The need to measure only SOC or separately total carbon (TC) and carbonates will depend on the laboratory instrument (e.g., automatic measurement of total carbon with catalytic high-temperature combustion, total inorganic carbon via acidification, and total organic carbon as their difference). In soils without carbonates as determined at Year 0, it will not be necessary to measure carbonates (total inorganic carbon) at Year 2 for calculating the content of SOC, meaning that carbonates should only be measured in alkaline soils.

Bulk density has been proposed as an indicator for the *threat to soil* of soil compaction or soil structural decline (European Commission, 2023; Evangelista et al., 2023), but it is also a potential indicator for the functions of production of food and biomass, and indirectly for storage and regulation of water through its relationship with soil porosity and infiltration capacity. The content of coarse fragments is more variable over short spatial range than over time. However, we recommend sampling coarse fragments and bulk density from the same soil sample (either by the cylinder method or the excavation method depending on the stoniness) simultaneously to SOC content, as these three variables are needed for calculating SOC stocks (Table 4). Finally, we acknowledge that detecting changes in SOC in a short period (less than 5 years) is challenging given the size of SOC stocks, inherent spatial and temporal SOC variability, rate of C gain in Mediterranean climate (Smith et al., 2020). Although we are constrained by the length of the project, we hope that the monitoring of changes in SOC will take place beyond the completion of LILAS4SOILS and according to the recommendations of the EU CRCF regulation (minimum 5 years), especially if the participating farmers can enlist in carbon farming programmes. This will be facilitated by the WP6, that will ensure the long-term sustainability and continuity of the LLs in their respective regions.

Table 4: Soil properties measured at the different sampling times. The variables needed to calculate SOC stocks are measured every sampling campaign.

Year 0 (2025)	Year 2 (2027)	Year 3 (2028)	Co-benefits / Soil functions
Particle size distribution			Carbon storage (Modelling C dynamics)
Coarse fragments	Coarse fragments	Coarse fragments	Carbon storage
Bulk density	Bulk density	Bulk density	<i>Soil compaction (threat)</i> Carbon storage
Soil Organic Carbon	Soil Organic Carbon	Soil Organic Carbon	Carbon storage
Total Carbon		Total Carbon	Carbon storage
Total Nitrogen		Total Nitrogen	Nutrient storage and regulation (Modelling carbon dynamics)
Carbonates		Carbonates	Carbon storage Nutrient storage and regulation (Modelling carbon dynamics)
pH		pH	Nutrient storage and regulation
Electrical conductivity		Electrical conductivity	<i>Salinisation (threat)</i> Water quality and regulation
Potential Mineralizable Nitrogen (PMN)		Potential Mineralizable Nitrogen (PMN)	Nutrient storage and regulation
Soil organic matter fractions (MAOM and POM)		Soil organic matter fractions (MAOM and POM)	Carbon storage Nutrient storage and regulation
Soil moisture at field water capacity (θ_{FC})		Soil moisture at field water capacity (θ_{FC})	Storage and regulation of water
Soil moisture at permanent wilting point (θ_{WP})		Soil moisture at permanent wilting point (θ_{WP})	Storage and regulation of water
16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing		16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing	Habitat of soil biodiversity

3.4 Protocol for field sampling

3.4.1. Conditions to select the interval of sampling dates

Soil properties (e.g., SOC, pH, soil microbial communities) responsive to management and climatic conditions have interannual and seasonal variability. Hence, the sampling campaigns must be conducted around the same month (or at least season) every sampling campaign.

In the Mediterranean, the soil can be very dry making it very difficult to operate with the soil auger or soil probe and taking intact cores. Some soil carbon MRV protocols recommend sampling in periods of low biological activity; in Mediterranean soils this may happen in summer due to the reduced soil moisture limiting the microbial activity. However, summer may be avoided for soil sampling because the time and physical effort needed for sampling will affect sampling efficiency and time management.

Sampling should avoid being conducted right after cultivation operations and practices that disturb the soil considerably or cause peaks in some soil processes and hence in soil properties used as indicators of co-benefits for CFPs (e.g. tillage, disking, seeding, fertilizer application) (Arrouays et al., 2018). Arrouays et al. (2018) recommended a minimum period of four weeks after the last ploughing for sampling in croplands. In addition, soil sampling should avoid occurring immediately before or after irrigation dates. Preferably, the soil should be close to field capacity and with firm layers (Arrouays et al., 2018). The soil should not be saturated (1-3 days after the last precipitation), and the water table below the lowest sampling depth limit (30 cm). The soil should not be saturated as these soils are more susceptible to compaction during sampling.

The sampled layers with LILAS4SOILS are 0-10 cm and 10-30 cm, following the minimum depth of 30 cm recommended by the IPCC to monitor SOC changes. We acknowledge that at perennial crops and agroforestry systems the deeper horizons can contribute significantly to the total SOC stock due to the effect of deep rooting systems, but we will exclude them from this protocol.

3.4.2. Field sampling

Before going to the field, the soil survey team needs the following material for soil sampling:

- Tablet/pad or printed table with theoretical coordinates of sampling units
- GPS
- Compass
- Flags/Sticks
- Measuring tape of 4 m (optional)
- Soil probe or soil auger of at least 30 cm length
- Spade with a 20 cm blade
- Small spade
- Field knife with flat blade
- Stainless steel rings + cylinder holder device
- Rubber mallet
- Permanent marker
- Two labelled reclosable plastic bags per sampling unit. The first for the 0-10 cm composite sample and a second one for the 10-30 cm composite sample.
- Two labelled reclosable plastic bags (or simple plastic bags) per sampling unit for bulk density samples, for the 0-10 cm and 10-30 cm depth interval respectively

- Four unlabelled reclosable plastic bags, for double-bagging the composite samples (one bag for the composite 0-10 cm, a second bag for the composite 10-30 cm, a third bag for two bags with the cylinders for bulk density. In the case of the excavation method, use one bag per bulk density sample and depth interval.
- Disposable laboratory gloves
- Paper towels
- Box to store and transport the samples
- A cooler with ice packs to preserve samples for PMN and 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing
- Plastic container (optional) – aggregate stability sample

Material for collecting bulk density samples with the excavation method:

- Short level (20 cm)
- Annular rigid template (15-20 cm diameter) with holes
- Nails for fixing the template to the soil
- Soup spoon or a small gardening shovel, ladle, brush
- Transparent, thin, strong, waterproof plastic bags
- 500 mL measuring cylinder graduated in 5 ml increments
- Water canister (5 l)
- Funnel

Information of field work conditions

Field conditions will be recorded at the field notes (e.g., weather, appearance of the sampling unit and evidence of recent agricultural practices). While sampling the organic horizon for laboratory analysis is not mandatory, the presence of litter layer/crop residues and thickness of organic horizons will be easily recorded, and they are an early indicator of the effects of CFPs on the soil. Take general pictures of the sampling unit, they can help months later to understand the data, especially when they are strange. Field notes can be written in a form similar to that presented in Annex B (prepared and shared by the team of Food4Sustainability, David Santos and colleagues).

Amount of composite sample and caution for avoiding cross-contamination

The amount of composite sample (minimum of 500-600 g) should be enough for carrying the whole set of laboratory analyses to determine SOC stock and indicators of soil functions listed as co-benefits (Table 4). In ideal conditions, the materials used to collect different composite samples should be different, or at least cleaned to avoid cross-contamination, for samples that will be analyses for soil microbial biodiversity (e.g., samples below tree canopies and outside tree canopies). However, cleaning instruments in the field is complicated and time consuming (e.g., cleaning with water and 70% ethanol, drying...). Hence, we remind the minimum good practices to remember when sampling for soil biodiversity (composite sample):

- **Avoid touching the composite samples with your hands**, use always a spade or similar instrument to push the soil probe/soil auger sample into the plastic bag. Otherwise, if you need your hands to

push the soil sample from the soil corer or soil auger, **use disposable laboratory gloves, a different pair of gloves per sampling unit!**

Sampling unit – circular plot

The centre of the sampling unit (circular plot of 4 m radius) is located following the coordinates of the GPS and marked with a flag (or plastic or wooden stick). Record the real location of the centre of the plot with the GPS. Near the centre of the plot, a soil pit is dug where samples for bulk density and coarse fragments are extracted following the steps explained in section 3.4.3 at the selected depth intervals (Figure 13). The size of the pit and method for sampling bulk density is adapted to the local conditions (Arrouays et al., 2018).

The soil thickness considered in this protocol is the 0-30 cm of mineral soils, sampled by fixed depth intervals. Soil samples will be taken for the depth intervals 0-10 cm and 10-30 cm. Only the top 0-10 cm layer will be analysed for soil microbial biodiversity (16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing).

When the soil thickness is less than 30 cm, we will **record the maximum depth**. For example, we could get a sample for 0-10 cm, and another from 0-20 cm.

Organic soil horizons are optional. Superficial stones, litter and grass, vegetation residues or agricultural amendments (e.g., straw), and the organic layer (O horizons) will be removed carefully with a spade, to not eliminate the superficial centimetres of the mineral soil (A or Ap horizon) (European Commission, 2017), before taking the samples of bulk density and samples for the composite.

In the proximity of the centre of the plot, but not right next to the pit (about 50 cm apart), the first sample for the composite is extracted with a soil probe or soil auger up to 30 cm depth (Figure 12 and Figure 13). If necessary, use the rubber mallet to push the soil probe. Turn the soil probe in clockwise direction and extract it. The sample is divided by depth interval into two previously labelled, reclosable plastic bags (0-10 cm and 10-30 cm respectively) with help of a field knife or spatula (Figure 12).

Figure 12: a) Soil probe is inserted up to 30 cm in the mineral soil. b) the soil sample is divided into two pre-labelled plastic bags for the 0-10 cm and 10-30 cm composite samples. Photo credit: Patricia Gallejones.

The additional sampling points for the composite sample are located at 2 m and 4 m from the centre of the plot in the four cardinal directions: North, South, East and West (Figure 13). In practice, we are located at the centre of the plot with a compass –which can be a physical compass or an app at the cell phone– and we identify one of the cardinal directions (e.g., North). We use the measuring tape or take two steps (approximately 2 m) into that direction to the second sampling point, where we take an additional soil sample with the probe. Flags can be useful to mark the location of the sampling points. The sample is partitioned by depth interval into their corresponding reclosable bags for the composite samples (Figure 12). We take two additional steps to reach 4 m from the centre of the plot, extract the third soil sample with the probe and partition it into the 0-10 cm and 10-30 cm composite samples. We return to the centre of the plot and identify the next cardinal direction (e.g., East) and take samples 4 and 5 with the same procedure. We repeat these steps until we have a composite sample from 9 sampling points (Figure 13). The principle to identify the sampling points is very similar to the field sampling manual for LUCAS, with four additional points at 4 m (European Commission, 2017).

Place each plastic bag with the composite sample inside a second plastic bag, to avoid cross-contamination in case the bag opens during transportation or is not properly closed. Similarly, place the plastic bags with the bulk density and coarse fragments sample inside a second plastic bag. Keep the samples inside a cooler with ice packs.

Soil pits for bulk density and coarse fragments should be refilled after field sampling, returning the soil layers with the same order of the original horizons (Arrouays et al., 2018).

Figure 13: A circular plot of 4 m radius constitutes the sampling unit. Nine sampling points for a composite sample are located at 2 m and 4 m into the cardinal directions and near the centre of the plot. A pit for sampling bulk density and coarse fragments is dug in the centre of the plot.

Sampling unit – transect

For alley cropping systems (e.g., orchards, olive groves in terraces), transect sampling units may be preferred to account for differences in SOC between the tree row and the inter row. As a simplification of

the composite sampling scheme proposed by Minarsch et al. (2024), composite samples will be made along two transects: one located in the tree line, a second one in the inter row (Figure 9 and Figure 14).

To guarantee that successive field campaigns sample the same approximate locations, at the tree row we will identify two key trees and the field team will record their coordinates. To collect a similar amount of soil per composite as with the circular plots (~500-600 g), we will collect eight samples with the auger: two soil samples around the key trees, two soil samples at half the distance between trees, and four samples at a quarter distance (Figure 9). All these samples will be combined into a composite for the tree row transect. An additional composite sample, that takes samples in zig-zag in the inter row (ranging between a quarter distance and the middle of the inter row) will be collected, parallel to those by the tree row transect following the same procedure.

The location for taking the bulk density and coarse fragments sample will be located at least one quarter of the distance between trees at the tree rows.

Place each plastic bag with the composite sample inside a second plastic bag, to avoid cross-contamination in case the bag opens during transportation or is not properly closed. Similarly, place the plastic bags with the bulk density and coarse fragments sample inside a second plastic bag. Keep the samples inside a cooler with ice packs.

As with the circular plots, the soil thickness considered in this protocol is the 0-30 cm of mineral soils, sampled by fixed depth intervals. Soil samples will be taken for the depth intervals 0-10 cm and 10-30 cm. Only the top 0-10 cm layer will be analysed for soil microbial biodiversity (16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing).

When the soil thickness is less than 30 cm, we will **record the maximum depth**. For example, we could get a sample for 0-10 cm, and another from 0-20 cm.

Organic soil horizons are excluded from the sampling. Superficial stones, litter and grass, vegetation residues or agricultural amendments (e.g., straw), and the organic layer (O horizons) will be removed carefully with a spade, to not eliminate the superficial centimetres of the mineral soil (A or Ap horizon) (European Commission, 2017), before taking the samples of bulk density and samples for the composite.

The steps followed for taking soil samples with the soil probe or soil auger are the same as at the circular plots. The same steps for taking samples for the composite (elimination of organic layers and stones, etc.) are applied for the dehesa/montado sampling approach. Remember to record the presence and thickness of the litter layer (O_L) and organic horizons (O_F , O_H).

Figure 14: Separation between samples along transects in alley crop systems for creating a composite.

Soil profile description and classification

Soil profile description and classification is an optional but desirable information that can help understanding not only the distribution of the soil genoforms or dominant soil type within the intervention area and need for stratification, but also possible limitations for the success of CFPs and expected changes on SOC over time. Soil description and classification is time consuming and requires high expertise. Therefore, it may not be possible due to time or skill constraints to carry this task across all living labs. However, we encourage this when possible. We recommend doing the description following the World Reference Base IUSS system (WRB, 2022).

Description of soil characteristics it is possible for the 0-30 cm when carrying the augering or digging of soil samples. The field surveyors should take notes of soil features that can be observed while doing the soil sampling: for instance, presence of a plough layer or redoximorphic features, presence and nature of nodules and concretions, lithology and degree of weathering of the coarse material, etc.

3.4.3. Sampling for bulk density and coarse fragments

Two methods are suggested for sampling bulk density depending on the stoniness: the core method (non-stony soils) and the excavation method (very stony soils). These two methods are included in the International Standard ISO-11272 for determination of bulk density, together with the clod method.

Core method

The core method is one of the most common methods for direct determination of bulk density (Blake and Hartge, 1986). Undisturbed soil core samples are collected using a stainless-steel coring ring of known volume taken vertically at each depth interval (0-10 cm and 10-30 cm).

Once the surface litter and grass, stones greater than 6 cm (European Commission, 2017), as well as organic horizon has been removed carefully raking with a small spade or a field knife, we place a coring ring with the bevelled edge down and we press it gently using a mallet. We can use a block of wood if the soil corer does not include a ring holder device (Figure 15). We will avoid compacting the soil by not pushing the ring too deep into the soil. To extract the cylinder, we dig around the coring ring with a spade, making four diggings at 2-3 cm from the ring, leaving the ring in the middle of a square. We deposit carefully the soil at the side of each hole, while not stepping or disturbing the area where the soil core is. When we have excavated at the four sides of the ring, we insert the spade underneath the ring to extract it (together with surrounding soil clump) to not disturb it and loosen the soil within. We remove the excess of soil from the bottom of the cylinder and outside the edge with the field knife (European Commission, 2017) and we cut with scissors the roots that stand out of the cylinder (FAO, 2020).

The length of the cylinder may be smaller than the thickness of the horizon being sampled (e.g., 51 mm cylinder, and 0-10 cm depth interval). **Hence, we can remove the top 2 cm of mineral soil before inserting the ring to sample the middle of the considered depth interval.**

Figure 15: The metallic ring has an adapter holding device (a piston) to facilitate sampling for bulk density. Photo credit: Patricia Gallejones.

Following the field recommendations for soil survey for LUCAS (European Commission, 2017), if the ring is not completely filled with soil (less than 10% missing due to loss of material when removing the ring or presence of a big stone) it is possible to fill the ring with removed soil. If more than 10% of the soil is missing, discard this sample and take a new sample in its proximity, where the soil has not been disturbed. Seal the ring with a plastic lid and mark it with the code of the sampling unit to avoid confusion. Place inside a plastic bag.

A common size for the cylinders is 100 cm³ which are suitable for soils with non or little amount of coarse fragments, since these are often underrepresented in small samples, leading to underestimation of bulk density in gravelly soils (FAO, 2020).

For the depth interval 10-30 cm, we repeat the same steps for sampling with the core method, digging to a depth near the middle of the layer (20 cm). We can profit from the holes that we made to extract the bulk density sample from the 0-10 cm, digging 10 cm more trying to **leave a horizontal and flat layer at 20 cm with a horizontal stroke**. For clarification, when the height of the cylinder is of 5 cm, we will take the sample between 20-25 cm.

When the soil thickness is less than 30 cm, we will **record the maximum depth**. For example, we could get a bulk density sample for 0-10 cm, and the second cylinder from 15-20 cm if the soil thickness was around 20 cm.

Excavation method

In very stony and incoherent soils, or root dense soils, the excavation method will be used for determination of bulk density following an adaptation of the International Standard ISO 11272 according to the French Soil Quality Monitoring Network Manual (Jolivet et al., 2022). The excavation method consists on creating a cavity in the soil, collecting all the extracted soil, and measuring the cavity's volume using water. The steps, which can be found with accompanying pictures in the referred manual, are the following:

1. Remove the surface litter and grass, stones greater than 6 cm, as well as organic horizon carefully raking with a small spade and level the surface with the spade, knife or similar instrument. Check that the surface is perfectly flat with the level before digging the cavity.
2. Place the annular template on the soil surface and secure it with nails. Check the flatness with the level.
3. Dig the cavity with a spoon, small garden shovel, or the help of a knife, and collect all the sample into a labelled bag. Use the brush to collect the soil that falls outside the bag on the annular template. The diameter of the cavity corresponds to that of the template (between 15-20 cm), and the depth should first be to 10 cm. The shape of the cavity does not have to be perfect, but try to keep regular edges, and avoid indentations that could break the plastic bag.
4. Place a thin plastic bag in the cavity and press it softly against the walls. Fill the graduated cylinder and record the volume. Pour water into the plastic bag, not yet up to the top of the cavity. Before, correct the position of the plastic bag within the cavity using your hands (using gloves) or the spoon. Once the plastic bag is correctly adhered to the walls, fill the plastic bag until the surface level is reached. Read the volume of water remaining in the graduated cylinder and calculate difference (i.e., the volume of water poured into the cavity).
5. To collect a sample between 10-30 cm, we can continue with the same cavity. We will label a second bag (10-30 cm) where we will place the second sample following the same steps, excavating with a small garden shovel or spoon.
6. We will place a plastic bag in the expanded cavity, and we will measure the volume of the whole cavity (0-30 cm) with water as in step 4. However, the volume for the layer 10-30 cm will be calculated as the difference between the volume 0-30 cm and the volume of the 0-10 cm cavity.

Additional resources to understand clearly the steps of the cavity method are found in several videos, for example by the USDA NRCS Soil and Plant Science Channel YouTube video entitled “How To Sample Bulk Density In The Field” (<https://youtu.be/E7BSZrJ-TDw?si=YI2zyCDw8NA1uGmg&t=1566>). Another example performed at the forest is the video “Soil Compaction – Excavation Method” by the Virtual Soil Science Learning Resources Channel of the university of British Columbia (<https://youtu.be/-jx1p-vSKil?si=BS7zjWZiyN5qzxC2>).

Place the bag with the sample inside a second reclosable plastic bag, to avoid possible spills and cross-contamination during transportation.

3.4.4. Sampling for soil moisture at field water capacity (θ_{FC}) and at permanent wilting point (θ_{PWP})

The ISO standard for determination of soil hydraulic properties (ISO 11274) includes different methods for working with altered or intact samples. If our laboratory works with altered sample for measuring soil water retention, we do not need to take an additional sample because we will use an aliquot from the composite sample. If the laboratory has the equipment for working with undisturbed soil clods ($\sim 10 \text{ cm}^3$), these can be sampled either with an additional intact core following the same procedure and depth intervals as for bulk density. Another option is to extract a “block” of soil with the help of the spade from a cleaned surface (previously gently raked with the spade) for each depth interval trying to use the natural cracks or structural divisions in the soil and place it in a plastic storage container to preserve the soil structure. We refer to the French Soil Quality Monitoring Network Manual RMQS2 (Jolivet et al., 2022) for detailed instructions. For the objectives of LILAS4SOILS, a smaller sample around 10 cm width would suffice compared to the block of soil about 20 cm width collected for the RMQS. At the laboratory, undisturbed soil clods can be extracted from the plastic container.

In soils with incoherent or very loose structure, high content of coarse fragments, coarse texture, or high content of roots and plant debris this method may be not feasible. Then, an intact core sample or measuring soil water retention characteristics from altered sample (composite) will be the option at the laboratory.

3.4.5. Pre-processing of samples and conservation of fresh sample for soil biodiversity analyses.

We will have two different sample types at arrival at the laboratory: composite samples (500-600 g) and bulk density sample (intact cores or excavation method) (Figure 16). We might have a third sample depending on the method for determination of θ_{PWP} and θ_{FC} (undisturbed or disturbed soil). If the water retention characteristics are determined from an undisturbed sample, we will have a second cylinder or a sealed container with soil to select soil clods with unaltered structure. Optionally, we can also collect a sample for measuring aggregate stability with the Slakes smartphone app following the instructions at the Soil Health Institute (<https://soilhealthinstitute.org/our-work/initiatives/slakes/>).

This section outlines the procedures for collecting soil samples for PMN and 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing. It is recommended that samples are paired with as many relevant environmental measurements as possible. To ensure representative sampling, the sample for soil biodiversity will originate from the composite sample made from all the sampling points within the same sampling unit, circular plot or transect (Section 3.2). Thus, the composite samples shall be transported to the laboratory as soon as possible and stored at 4°C. A subsample from the composite sample (~100 g) will be preserved fresh while the remaining (450-550 g) will be air-dried. Then, it is important to follow these steps:

- Remember, **PMN is performed for the two depths (0-10 cm and 10-30 cm) soil microbiome analyses only on the 0-10 cm**. Hence, we need 100 g of fresh sample from the 0-10 cm (e.g., one falcon tube of 50 g for PMN and one falcon tube 50 g for soil microbiome), and 50 g of fresh sample from the 10-30 cm (e.g., one falcon tube 50 g for PMN).
- Upon arrival to the laboratory, or as soon as possible, homogenise the composite sample and sieve a representative subsample of fresh soil (50-100 g) through a 2-mm mesh to separate the fine fraction (< 2mm). All materials used to sieve soil samples to be used for diversity analyses need to be rinsed with 70% ethanol to prevent cross-contamination. These **50-100 g that will be kept as fresh sample**. Sieved samples should be **stored at 4°C**.
- Prior sending samples to DNA extraction and 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing, prepare a representative 10 g aliquot of fresh soil from the 0-10 cm. Cold shipping is mandatory, including cold packs.
- If DNA extraction is not to be carried out immediately, it is preferable to **freeze a representative 10 g aliquot of the fresh sample from 0-10 cm (for 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing) at -20 °C**. However, freezing and thawing should be avoided by doing the DNA extractions rapidly after sampling.
- The remaining 40-60 g of fresh soil will be stored fresh at 4°C and used later for PMN analysis.

The remaining of composite sample (~450-550 g) will be air dried and sieved to separate coarse fragments (> 2mm). Some laboratories may prefer to dry the sample in the oven at low temperature, not greater than 40°C as this can alter some determinations. During sieving, we will pay attention for breaking aggregates > 2mm that may be confused with coarse fragments. The air-dried composite sample will be later used for measurement of particle size distribution, SOC, TC, TN, carbonates, pH, EC, and SOC fractions (and most likely θ_{PWP} and θ_{FC}).

The intact core for determination of bulk density, or the excavation method sample is processed by oven drying at 105°C, weighed for determination of whole soil bulk density (see section 3.5) and processed for determination of coarse fragment content (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Flow chart with the different sample types and pre-processing for determination of biological and physico-chemical parameters.

3.5 Laboratory analyses and calculations of soil properties

The preferred methods are gathered from general protocols for monitoring soil health indicators like the EU Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive (SMD) (European Commission, 2023) and the FAO-GSOC MRV Protocol (FAO, 2020).

Table 5: Preferred soil analysis methods and International Standard or literature references for estimating indicators of soil functions, or co-benefits derived from soil-farming practices, and calculating SOC stocks.

Soil properties	Laboratory method	Type of sample (pre-processing)	Reference
Particle size distribution	Laser diffraction Method by sieving and sedimentation	Air dry	ISO 13320 ISO 11277

Coarse fragments	Gravimetry	Oven dried at 105°C	ISO 11272, Jolivet et al. (2022)
Bulk density	Gravimetry	Oven dried at 105°C	ISO 11272, Jolivet et al. (2022)
Total Carbon	High-temperature catalysed combustion	Air dry	ISO 10694
Soil Organic Carbon	High-temperature catalysed combustion	Air dry	ISO 10694
Total Nitrogen	High-temperature catalysed combustion	Air dry	ISO 13878
Carbonates	Calcimeter	Air dry	ISO 10693
pH	Potentiometry	Air dry	ISO 10390
Electrical Conductivity	Conductivity meter	Air dry	ISO 11265 FAO SOP: GLOSOLAN-SOP-0876
Potential Mineralizable Nitrogen (PMN)	Spectrophotometry	Fresh (4°C)	Canali and Benedetti (2005); Mulvaney (1996); Powers (1980)
Soil organic matter fractions (MAOM and POM)	Size fractionation	Air dry	Cotrufo et al. (2019)
Soil moisture at field water capacity (θ_{FC})	Pressure plate	Air dry (rewetted during procedure)	ISO 11274
Soil moisture at permanent wilting point (θ_{PWP})	Pressure plate	Air dry (rewetted during procedure)	ISO 11274
16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing	DNA extraction, PCR amplification, sequencing, data processing and taxonomic classification	Fresh (4°C if extraction immediate, -20 or -80 °C if extraction will be performed after several days or weeks).	NEIKER

Particle size distribution

The preferred methods for particle size distribution are sieving and sedimentation (ISO 11277) or laser diffraction (ISO 13320). Particle size fraction will be used as input variables for modelling SOC dynamics and predicting the effects of CFPs on SOC stocks with a hybrid approach.

Soil texture influences SOC storage through the role of the mineral matrix on physico-chemical stabilization mechanisms, especially clay minerals and fine silt particles (Lützow et al., 2006; Six et al., 2002). Soil texture also controls soil hydraulic properties and is often used for estimating soil moisture at field capacity (θ_{FC}) and permanent wilting point (θ_{PWP}) with pedotransfer functions (Cousin et al., 2022; Van Looy et al., 2017), that often allow to propagate uncertainties and assess its applicability domain (Román Dobarco et al., 2019; Szabó et al., 2021).

Bulk density

Following the extraction of intact soil cores or the excavation method at the field, the determination of dry bulk density at the laboratory is done with the international standard ISO 11272. The intact soil core (or sample excavated) is oven-dried at 105°C for at least 24 hours to eliminate soil moisture and weighted. Bulk density of the whole soil is calculated as the ratio of dried soil mass to its known volume (Blake and Hartge, 1986):

$$\rho_{Wh} = \frac{mass_{soil}}{V_{soil}} \quad [5]$$

Where ρ_{Wh} is the bulk density of the whole soil (g cm^{-3}) while $mass_{soil}$ is the dry mass of the soil core and V_{soil} the known inner volume of the sampled soil cylinder (cm^3). Sometimes bulk density is reported in Mg m^{-3} .

When the sample is taken with the excavation method, we proceed with similar calculation, recording the mass of the oven-dried bulk soil (fine earth + coarse fragments) and the volume measured in the cavity using water.

Several protocols calculate the bulk density of the fine earth ($< 2 \text{ mm}$) and use it in subsequent SOC stocks calculations (e.g., (FAO, 2020)). The mass of the fine earth ($mass_{fine}$) is easily obtained by sieving the bulk soil from the intact core through a 2-mm mesh followed by calculation, subtracting the mass of coarse fragments to the mass of the bulk dry soil. However, the volume of fine earth is not always measured. Only in case the intact soil core has no coarse fragments both bulk densities would be identical. Otherwise, the volume of fine earth can be calculated by subtracting the volume of coarse fragments from the volume of the whole sample. If the volume of the coarse fragments has not been measured it can be estimated assuming an average density of coarse fragments around 2.65 g cm^{-3} (Hurlbut and Klein, 1977; McKenzie et al., 2002):

$$\rho_{fine} = \frac{mass_{fine}}{V_{fine}} = \frac{mass_{soil} - mass_{coarse}}{V_{soil} - \frac{mass_{coarse}}{\rho_{coarse}}} \quad [6]$$

Where ρ_{fine} is the bulk density of fine earth ($< 2 \text{ mm}$), V_{fine} is the volume of cylinder occupied by fine earth ($< 2 \text{ mm}$) and ρ_{coarse} is the density of coarse fragments. While using the density of the fine earth can ease calculations of stocks, assuming the same density for all coarse fragments irrespective of their lithology type is a source of error.

Coarse fragments

The gravimetric coarse fragments content and bulk density are determined from the same intact core, or sample taken with the excavation method. After the weight of the oven-dried bulk soil sample has been recorded ($mass_{soil}$) (fine earth $< 2 \text{ mm}$ + coarse fragments $> 2 \text{ mm}$) to calculate the bulk density, the bulk soil is sieved through a 2-mm mesh, aggregates greater than 2 mm in size are destroyed and washed to remove fine particles $< 2 \text{ mm}$. In very clayey soils, the elements $> 2 \text{ mm}$ can be soaked in a tray with hot water so that aggregates dissolve and coarse fragments can be better estimated. Some laboratories have automated mechanisms to sieve, destroy aggregates (not necessarily pulverising all rock fragments $> 2 \text{ mm}$) and wash coarse fragments (e.g., shaker sieve together with a wet sieving system). The gravimetric content of coarse fragments ($> 2 \text{ mm}$) is calculated as the ratio of the dry mass of coarse fragments ($> 2 \text{ mm}$) divided by the dry mass of the bulk soil ($mass_{soil}$) (fine earth + coarse fragments) and expressed in percentage (or as unitless ratio).

The mass of the coarse fragments ($mass_{coarse}$) is recorded and used to estimate the gravimetric percentage of coarse fragments (CF_{grav}) that will be used for SOC stocks calculations:

$$CF_{grav}(\%) = \frac{mass_{coarse}}{mass_{soil}} \times 100 \quad [4]$$

Note that other methods can be used to measure or estimate the volumetric content of coarse fragments but it is important to differentiate both, due to the effects on SOC stock calculations as *volumetric coarse*

fragment content needs to be combined with the *bulk density of the fine earth* (Poeplau et al., 2017) (see section 4).

Total C, carbonates and SOC content

TC and SOC content can be determined with the international standard ISO 10694 by dry combustion. Carbonate content can be determined following ISO 10693. The content of carbonates may be significant in alkaline soils. TC is determined with an elementary analyser (e.g., Soli Toc Cube, ELEMENTAR) with the combustion method. The composite sample should be well homogenised and finely grinded before taking a small aliquot for the automatic analyser. Total inorganic carbon (TIC) and total organic carbon (TOC) can also be determined by catalysed combustion along a temperature ramp (400°C for organic carbon, 600°C for residual organic carbon and 900°C for TIC).

Total N

Total N can be determined via high-temperature combustion with an elemental analyser according to ISO 13878. We prefer this method over the modified Kjeldahl method proposed by the SMD (European Commission, 2023) as it is more time efficient and can be determined simultaneously to SOC. A key argument for choosing total nitrogen determination by combustion instead of the Kjeldahl method in soils is its higher accuracy and ability to detect all nitrogen forms.

The Kjeldahl method only measures organic and ammoniacal nitrogen, ignoring other forms such as nitrates and nitrites, which can lead to an underestimation of total nitrogen content in soil samples. In contrast, combustion analysis (typically using an elemental analyzer) completely oxidizes all organic matter and converts all nitrogen present in the sample into nitrogen oxides or N_2 , which are quantified with high precision.

Moreover, combustion is faster, does not require hazardous reagents (such as sulfuric acid and metallic catalysts used in Kjeldahl), and is more environmentally friendly, making it a better choice for routine and high-precision soil analysis.

pH

Soil pH can be measured from air-dried soil samples (composite sample) using the international standard ISO 10390. In alignment with the SMD (European Commission, 2023) we will determine pH- H_2O . pH is determined with a glass electrode in a 1:5 (v/v) suspension of soil in water (pH in H_2O).

Electrical conductivity

Electrical conductivity (EC) has been included in the EU Soil Monitoring Law and an indicator for the threat of salinisation, which often occurs under irrigated soils in Mediterranean countries. Measuring EC can be done simultaneously to pH and can inform of the risk of incipient salinisation. We recommend the same method as the EU SML, following the ISO 11265 for determination of the specific EC or with a saturated soil paste extract (eEC) measurement method (FAO SOP: GLOSOLAN-SOP-0876).

Potential Mineralizable Nitrogen (PMN)

Potential mineralizable Nitrogen (PMN) is a measure of the fraction of organic nitrogen that is readily available for decomposition by microorganisms, making it available for plant growth. PMN is an indicator of soil fertility and nutrient availability and cycling. PMN can be an important indicator for organic farming practices that avoid synthetic fertilizers. In aerobic conditions, PMN is available to plants and microorganisms mainly as nitrate, whereas in anaerobic conditions it is mainly available as ammonium.

There are different methods for determination of PMN via soil incubation in aerobic or anaerobic conditions for several days. With the method of anaerobic incubation, 2.8 ml of distilled water is added to 1.5 g of fresh soil sample, sieved at 2 mm, eliminating bubbles, and it is kept for 7 days at 40 °C. The concentration of inorganic N ($\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$) is measured after KCl extraction. The samples are shaken for 1 hour after the addition of 1M KCl (1:5 soil-to-extractant ratio). The extracts are centrifuged and analysed for NH_4^+ by spectrophotometry. The analysis of PMN will be done on two laboratory replicates.

Soil organic matter (SOM) fractions

The SOM fractions, mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM) and particulate organic matter (POM) are obtained with physical fractionation following a modification of the protocol proposed by Cotrufo et al. (2019). The difference with the original protocol is that sodium hexametaphosphate is not included as dispersion agent, only glass beads are used for breaking aggregates and completely disperse the soil. Briefly, 5 g of air-dried (at room temperature 20°C-28°C) fine earth (< 2 mm) are mixed with 100 ml of deionized water and 4-5 g of glass beads of approximately 3 mm diameter, and shaken for 16 hours with an automated shaker (Figure 17). The soil slurry is then rinsed through a 50 µm sieve. The fraction passing through the sieve (<50 µm) corresponds to MAOM, whereas the fraction greater than 50 µm is defined as POM. Both fractions are oven dried at 55 °C until constant weight. POM and MAOM fractions are analysed for organic carbon with an elemental analyser. The mass and SOC recovery percentage will be calculated, with acceptable ranges of 95-100 % and 85-115 % respectively.

Figure 17: Diagram of soil organic matter physical fractionation.

Soil moisture at field water capacity (θ_{FC}) and at permanent wilting point (θ_{PWP})

Soil moisture at field capacity (θ_{FC}) and at permanent wilting point (θ_{PWP}) is determined with the pressure plate method following ISO 11274. The SMD suggests the ISO 11274 or estimating θ_{FC} and θ_{PWP} with the set of pedotransfer functions for Europe developed by Tóth et al. (2015), which were updated by Szabó et al. (2021) providing uncertainty estimates.

At the laboratory, θ_{FC} is determined from disturbed or undisturbed soil samples, clods of approximate volume 10 cm³ from each depth interval (0-10 cm and 10-30 cm). The soil clods are equilibrated at pre-determined matric potentials using a Richards pressure-plate apparatus for several days (ISO 11274:2019 recommends 5-7 days) (Cousin et al., 2022). The soil clods are then weighed: i) immediately after extraction from the pressure-plate (wet weight at a determined matric potential), and ii) after they have been dried at 105°C for 48 h (dry weight) to determine the gravimetric soil water content (Cousin et al., 2022). The traditionally recognised soil matric potential for permanent wilting point is -1500 kPa (pF = 4.2) (Richards and Weaver, 1943), whereas field capacity is assumed to be the soil moisture at -33 kPa or -10 kPa (pF = 2.5 and pF = 2.0) (Bruand et al., 2004; Cousin et al., 2022). In LILAS4SOILS we will determine field capacity with the soil moisture at -33 kPa. Cousin et al. (2022) recommend using undisturbed soil samples for determination of θ_{FC} as the clod retains unaltered its structure, whereas θ_{PWP} can be measured from sieved or disturbed samples.

16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing

DNA extraction. Use the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Qiagen) for DNA extraction (<https://www.qiagen.com/us/products/discovery-and-translational-research/dna-rna-purification/dna-purification/microbial-dna/dneasy-powersoil-pro-kit?catno=47014>) following the manufacturer's instructions, starting from 0.25 g of soil and with a final elution volume of 100 µL.

DNA quantification and quality check. DNA quality should be checked with NanoDrop, OD 260/280 should be between 1.8-2.0. A Qubit fluorometer or similar is preferred for quantification, with a minimum requirement of 10 ng µL-1 **PCR and sequencing.** The recommended PCR primer set for amplifying the V4-V5 region of the 16S rRNA gene as in LUCAS :

- Forward primer 515F: 5'-GTGCCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA-3'
- Reverse primer 926R: 5'-CCGYCAATTYMTTTRAGTTT -3'

Carry out PCR reactions with 15 µL of Phusion High - Fidelity PCR Master Mix, 0.2 µM of forward and reverse primers and about 10 ng template DNA. Thermal cycling consists of an initial denaturation at 98 °C for 1 min, followed by 30 cycles of denaturation at 98 °C for 10 s, annealing at 50 °C for 30 s, and elongation at 72 °C for 30 s and 72 °C for 5 min.

Purify the PCR products using magnetic bead purification. Mix samples in equidensity ratios based on the concentration of PCR products.

While sequencing providers may vary, we recommend using a service that employs Illumina sequencing platforms.

Each sample should yield a minimum of 50,000 sequence reads. Raw sequences should be deposited to the European Nucleotide Archive and/or Zenodo.

Bioinformatics. Assign paired-end reads to samples based on their unique barcode and truncate by cutting off the barcode and primer sequences. Merge paired-end reads using FLASH (<http://ccb.jhu.edu/software/FLASH/>) (Magoč and Salzberg, 2011). Quality filter the raw tags using the fastp software to obtain high-quality Clean Tags (Bokulich et al., 2013). Compare the tags with the Silva reference database (<https://www.arb-silva.de/>) to detect chimera sequences, then obtain the Effective Tags by removing the chimera sequences with the vsearch package (<https://github.com/torognes/vsearch>) (Edgar et al., 2011). For the Effective Tags obtained previously, denoise with DADA2 module in the QIIME2 software to obtain initial ASVs (Amplicon Sequence Variants). Perform species annotation using QIIME2 software and Silva Database.

3.6 Limitations of the current protocol and additional soil indicators

The list of indicators selected in this protocol is not exhaustive. Additional soil properties that we wish to measure given available resources, among many others, include the following:

Physical properties

- **Aggregate stability.** Aggregate stability is a physical indicator that informs of the development of soil structure and is quite sensitive to management. The recent development of inexpensive and fast methods to measure aggregate stability with a smartphone makes this property very easy to measure (Fajardo et al., 2025; Flynn et al., 2020). Tutorials on how to perform aggregate stability analysis with the app Slakes can be found at the Soil Health Institute website (<https://soilhealthinstitute.org/our-work/initiatives/slakes/>). Note that performing this analysis would require an additional clod sample from the superficial soil layer (0- 5 cm) of which we would take three aggregates of about 0.3 cm - 1 cm diameter. The aggregates need to be undisturbed. Hence, since the composite sample used for most analyses will be disturbed and have aggregates destroyed, we need a separate sample.
- **Penetrometer.** Penetrometry tests can be included in the set of field analyses to assess: i) homogeneity of the intervention area, ii) variations in the sampling depth and avoid mistakes (e.g., sample for bulk density taken between 10 and 20 cm when there is a plough pan or cemented horizon, or stone layer), iii) to measure variations due to CFPs. Penetrometer tests can inform of compaction problems.

Chemical properties

- **O horizon.** Several CFPs considered at LILAS4SOILS (e.g., cover crops, reduced tillage) may have a noticeable effect on the thickness, type and C content of the O horizon. Sampling and characterizing the O horizon is recommended. At minimum, the field work team can record at the field notes the presence, type, and thickness of the O horizon layers (O_L, O_F and O_H).
 - We can use a cylinder (same type as used for sampling bulk density) placed randomly in proximity of each sampling points used for the composite sample (n = 9) to capture the spatial heterogeneity of the organic horizon.

- We will place the cylinder on the soil surface and take a sample with the help of the hammer and wood block if necessary, inserted few cm into the mineral soil, and extract the cylinder. Carefully extract the sample from the cylinder with the help of a knife or spatula.
- Record thickness of the whole O horizon and of the litter layer (O_L horizon) in the field notes.
- Separate and collect the litter layer (O_L) into a labelled plastic bag.
- Separate and discard the mineral or organo-mineral soil from the overlying O_F and O_H horizons with a knife. Place the O_F and O_H into a labelled plastic bag.
- Store in the cooler and bring to the lab for measuring the dry mass, and total C and N analyses.

Biological properties

- **Fungi ITS.** Determination of soil fungal biodiversity should be measured to complement the soil bacterial biodiversity analyses. In addition, soil fungal communities are very sensitive to land use and management, and anthropogenic pressure (Labouyrie et al., 2023). Soil fungal community is very relevant for multiple soil functions like C storage or nutrient regulation and storage. While LUCAS uses the full-length ITS region as it offers more accurate taxonomic resolution than the ITS2 region (Tedersoo et al., 2022), this would require additional funding. Hence, we recommend performing ITS analysis as outlined by the Earth Microbiome Project using the primers 1FF-1FR (5'-CTTGTCATTTAGAGGAAGTAA-3', 5'-GCTGCGTTCTTCATCGATGC-3') (White et al., 1990) and following the same procedure described above for 16S rRNA.
- **Microbial biomass.** Microbial biomass is generally measured with the fumigation extraction method (Vance et al., 1987). Microbial biomass informs of organic matter cycling and carbon storage, given the processes mediated by the microbial community, which also contribute to soil structure maintenance. Bünemann et al. (2018) summarised the advantages and disadvantages of this indicator in: sensitivity and relationship with other soil indicators, although it is spatially variable, difficult interpretation, and can provide contradictory results. The link to functionality can be unclear.
- **Enzymatic analysis.** The extraction of enzymes and cultivation with different substrates would inform of the effect of the CFPs on the function of nutrient regulation, cycling and storage and carbon storage. The interest of including these properties relies on its relationship with several indicators, its high sensitivity, while it is a simple and inexpensive method (Bünemann et al., 2018). However, some disadvantages are that the results may be contradictory, the behaviour for each enzyme is complex and variable, and it informs of the potential activity, not the current activity at the soil.
- **C mineralization.** There are several methods for estimating C mineralization, over different time intervals. This indicator informs about the function of carbon storage, and is also proxy of nutrient storage and regulation, and soil biodiversity. The 24-hour potential C mineralization has proven to be a meaningful indicator of soil health (Bagnall et al., 2023).
- **Soil Biological Quality-arthropod (SBQ-ar) index.** The SBQ-ar is very sensitive to land use and agricultural management (Menta et al., 2018), and it is a direct measure of soil biodiversity and a soil health indicator (Parisi et al., 2005). The challenge is that the characterization of arthropods requires skilled specialists on arthropod taxonomy.
- **Community Level Physiological Profiling.** This analysis can be easily done with Biolog™ or MicroResp™ microplates, and it is based on the utilization of different carbon sources by the

microbial community. It is a proxy for soil biodiversity and nutrient cycling, regulation and storage. While CLPP with Biolog informs more about the potential functionality, MicroResp may be closer to in situ conditions and requires less time for measurements (Bünemann et al., 2018). However, the results can be highly variable, requiring a high number of replicates.

4. Calculation of SOC stocks

4.1 Calculation of SOC stocks at an intervention area and a given year

The formulas to calculate the estimators of the population of interest change depending on the sampling design. We are assuming at this section that we apply stratified random sampling. We start by calculating the SOC stock at a single soil sampling unit

The SOC density (Mg C ha^{-1}) for depth layer i at a sampling unit is calculated as:

$$SOC_{density,i} = SOC_i \times \rho_{Wh,i} \times (1 - CF_{grav,i}) \times thickness_i \times 0.1 \quad [7]$$

Where SOC_i is the SOC content of the fine earth ($< 2 \text{ mm}$) (mg C g^{-1} soil $< 2\text{mm}$), $\rho_{Wh,i}$ is the bulk density of whole soil (g soil cm^{-3}) at layer i , $CF_{grav,i}$ is the ratio of gravimetric coarse fragments to bulk soil (hence units of $1 - CF_{grav,i}$ is $\text{g soil } < 2\text{mm} / \text{g soil}$) at depth interval i , $thickness_i$ is the thickness of depth interval i (cm) and 0.1 the conversion factor ($1 \text{ mg C cm}^{-2} = 0.1 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1}$). Notice that when the bulk density is of the fine earth, the coarse fragments ratio is volumetric (Poeplau et al., 2017), otherwise there would be a systematic error of the SOC stocks.

Alternatively, if the $mass_{fine}$ has been determined from a sample (e.g., intact core) of known volume, equation 7 can be simplified to equation 8 as per Poeplau et al. (2017):

$$SOC_{density,i} (\text{Mg C ha}^{-1}) = SOC_i (\text{mg C g}_{soil < 2\text{mm}}^{-1}) \times \frac{mass_{fine} (\text{g}_{soil < 2\text{mm}})}{V_{soil} (\text{cm}^3)} \times thickness_i (\text{cm}) \times 0.1 \left(\frac{\text{Mg C cm}^2}{\text{mg C ha}} \right) \quad [8]$$

With simple random sampling within strata, the estimator of the mean SOC stock density for each stratum h and depth interval i is the unweighted sample mean (Arrouays et al., 2018b; Brus, 2022):

$$\widehat{SOC}_{h,i} = \overline{SOC}_{S_{h,i}} = \frac{1}{n_{h,i}} \sum_{k \in S_{h,i}} SOC_{k,h,i} \quad [9]$$

where $\widehat{SOC}_{h,i}$ is the mean SOC density for the stratum h and depth interval i , $\overline{SOC}_{S_{h,i}}$ is the unweighted mean of the sample $S_{h,i}$, $n_{h,i}$ is the number of sampling units in stratum h , k is a sampling unit from the sample $S_{h,i}$, and $SOC_{k,h,i}$ is the SOC density of sampling unit k and depth interval i from stratum h calculated with equation 7.

The estimator of the mean SOC density (Mg C ha^{-1}) at the intervention area is calculated with the formula for the stratified random sampling, averaging the values from each stratum with their relative weights:

$$\widehat{SOC}_i = \sum_{h=1}^H w_h \widehat{SOC}_{h,i} \quad [10]$$

where \widehat{SOC}_i is the estimator of the mean SOC stock density for depth interval i , H is the total number of strata, w_h is the weight for stratum h . When the allocation of sampling units has been done proportional to the area, w_h is the relative area of the stratum, and if the stratification was done with equal area geostrata the weights are the same across all strata.

The sampling variance is a measurement of the random error associated to the sampling strategy, and it quantifies our uncertainty about the population mean, i.e., the mean SOC density at an intervention area

(Brus, 2022). The square root of the sampling variance is the standard error. The sampling variance of the mean SOC density for the intervention area is obtained by weighted averaging of the sampling variances of each stratum. The weights must be squared (Brus, 2022):

$$\hat{V}(\widehat{SOC}_i) = \sum_{h=1}^H w_h^2 \hat{V}(\widehat{SOC}_{h,i}) \quad [11]$$

Where $\hat{V}(\widehat{SOC}_{h,i})$ is the estimated sampling variance of the mean SOC density of stratum h and layer i (Arrouays et al., 2018b; Brus, 2022):

$$\hat{V}(\widehat{SOC}_{h,i}) = \frac{1}{n_h(n_h-1)} \sum_{k=1}^{n_h} (SOC_{k,h,i} - \widehat{SOC}_{h,i})^2 \quad [12]$$

4.2 Equivalent soil mass

Temporal changes on soil bulk density are expected as a result from the CFPs that may hinder the effects of the CFPs on the estimated change in SOC stocks. Therefore, it is recommended to provide the SOC stocks in equivalent soil mass (ESM) basis as recommended by some SOC MVR standards (FAO, 2020; Verra, 2024) and the scientific literature (Bradford et al., 2023; Von Haden et al., 2020; Wendt and Hauser, 2013). With the ESM approach, the SOC stocks are assessed relative to a constant soil mass per unit area, expressed as $Mg\ ha^{-1}$, and possible changes in bulk density are compensated by changes in sampled depth (Loubet et al., 2025). For a specific depth interval i , the mass of fine earth per unit area (FSS_i) is calculated dividing the dry mass of the fine earth ($mass_{fine,i}$) by the area sampled by the probe or auger, S_i (Wendt and Hauser, 2013). The SOC mass of a depth interval i per unit area, $M_{SOC,i}$, is the product of the fine earth mass and SOC content:

$$M_{SOC,i} = FSS_i \times SOC_i \times 10^{-3} \quad [13]$$

Where $M_{SOC,i}$ is expressed in $Mg\ C\ ha^{-1}$, the mass of fine earth (FSS_i) is expressed in $Mg\ ha^{-1}$ and the content of SOC in fine earth, SOC_i is in $g\ C\ kg_{soil<2mm}^{-1}$, with the conversion factor 10^{-3} kg soil to Mg soil and g C to Mg C. We can express equation 13 from the measurements of the soil auger sample:

$$M_{SOC,i} = FSS_i \times SOC_i = \frac{mass_{fine,i}}{S_i} \times SOC_i = \frac{mass_{fine,i}}{\pi \left(\frac{D}{2}\right)^2} \times SOC_i \quad [14]$$

Where the mass of fine earth, $mass_{fine,i}$, corresponds to the mass from the sample (e.g., cylinder or auger) in g, the sampled area is in cm^2 , the SOC_i the content of SOC in $mg\ C\ g_{soil<2mm}^{-1}$, D is the inner diameter of the cylinder (cm). indicating the units and the conversion factor in equation 14:

$$M_{SOC,i}(Mg\ C\ ha^{-1}) = \frac{mass_{fine,i}(g_{soil<2mm})}{\pi \left(\frac{D}{2}\right)^2 (cm^2)} \times SOC_i (mg\ C\ g_{soil<2mm}^{-1}) \times 0.1 \left(\frac{Mg\ C\ cm^2}{mg\ C\ ha}\right) \quad [15]$$

Because we are sampling the depth intervals 0-10 cm and 10-30 cm, the cumulative SOC stock of 0-30 cm is calculated and then transformed into SOC stock for a reference soil mass that is maintained constant over sampling times. For the ESM calculation, since there are only 0-10 cm and 10-30 cm sub-layers, it might be necessary to include 0.0 cm as a depth so the spline can be fitted. Values for the reference soil

mass can be that from the decompacted situation after project development (FAO, 2020), or soil mass at initial conditions (Loubet et al., 2025). Wendt and Hauser (2013) provided a spreadsheet to estimate the ESM using a cubic spline function. Von Haden et al. (2020) developed an R script that uses cubic spline interpolations and mineral soil masses to calculate ESM-based SOC stocks. Similarly, Ferchaud et al. (2023) developed the R script *SimpleESM* to ease calculations of ESM-based SOC stocks.

4.3 Calculation of SOC stock change

The change of the mean SOC stocks between two sampling times t_1 and t_0 ($\overline{\Delta SOC}$) is calculated as the spatial mean of SOC stock for a given time (\widehat{SOC}_{t_1}) minus the spatial mean SOC stock from a previous survey (\widehat{SOC}_{t_0}).

$$\overline{\Delta SOC} = \widehat{SOC}_{t_1} - \widehat{SOC}_{t_0} \quad [16]$$

We are using a static synchronous approach, and the same soil sampling units are revisited in consecutive campaigns. Hence, we calculate the change in SOC stock at each sampling unit k , followed by averaging by stratum h and at the intervention area with weights proportional to strata areas.

$$\overline{\Delta SOC} = \sum_{h=1}^H w_h \widehat{\Delta SOC}_h = \sum_{h=1}^H w_h \frac{1}{n_h} \sum_{k=1}^{n_h} \Delta SOC_k \quad [17]$$

The variance of the mean change in SOC stock can be derived from the properties of variance:

$$\hat{V}(\overline{\Delta SOC}) = \hat{V}(\widehat{SOC}_{t_1}) + \hat{V}(\widehat{SOC}_{t_0}) - 2Cov(\widehat{SOC}_{t_1}, \widehat{SOC}_{t_0}) \quad [18]$$

Where $\hat{V}(\widehat{SOC}_{t_1})$ and $\hat{V}(\widehat{SOC}_{t_0})$ are respectively the variances of the mean SOC stock for time t_1 and t_0 calculated with equation 12, and $Cov(\widehat{SOC}_{t_1}, \widehat{SOC}_{t_0})$ is the covariance of the two mean estimators (Brus, 2014). Please note that with an independent synchronous design, where the probability samples at t_1 and t_0 are located at different locations, the covariance term can be considered zero.

4.4 Monitoring changes in SOC

4.9.2. Measure and Re-measure

The specific initial SOC stocks are measured at intervention areas at Year 0 and controls where the soil characteristics, relief, climate and agricultural system are similar to the intervention area. It is possible that at the control site and at the intervention area some practices of conservation agriculture or regenerative agriculture are already adopted (e.g., reduced tillage). The management at Year 0 defines our baseline conditions. However, we assume additional practices that will further improve soil condition and carbon storage will be adopted only at the intervention area (e.g., improved crop rotation). The SOC stocks can be remeasured at Year 2 and Year 3 at both controls and intervention areas, allowing for the incorporation of dynamic baselines (Bradford et al., 2023). This is particularly important for cases where process-based models are not sufficiently calibrated or validated. The significance of the changes in SOC stocks at the

intervention area can be assessed with a t-test with the adequate degrees of freedom (Loubet et al., 2025). The t-value is calculated as:

$$t = \frac{\overline{SOC}_{t0} - \overline{SOC}_{t1}}{\sqrt{V(\overline{SOC}_{t0}) + V(\overline{SOC}_{t1}) - 2Cov(\overline{SOC}_{t1}, \overline{SOC}_{t0})}} \quad [19]$$

Where the variance refers to the sampling variance at the intervention area (accounting for the sample size). As in equation 18, when the space-time sampling design is independent synchronous, the covariance term between the two independent probability samples for t0 and t1 can be considered negligible.

4.9.1. Measure and Model

The specific initial SOC stocks at the intervention areas are measured for Year 0 (sampling campaign from 2025) before the implementation of CFPs. Measure and model approaches use robust and validated process-based models (e.g., RothC, AGM, ORCHIDEE) for predicting changes in SOC stocks caused by the CFPs. These models should be able to simulate the effects of extreme climatic events (e.g., droughts) on SOC dynamics that can explain SOC accrual or losses different than those due solely to the carbon farming project implementation. The ARMOSA process-based crop model (Perego et al., 2013) has been used to assess the effects of conservation agriculture on SOC dynamics in comparison to conventional agricultural practices (Valkama et al., 2020) using as input data on climate, soil properties, management and crop type. The simulations allow to assess the effects of carbon farming on SOC stocks and GHG emissions in comparison with the baseline scenario (conventional agriculture) for the top 0-30 cm of mineral soil. This protocol will serve to measure the soil properties needed to initialize the model (soil texture, SOC, N, SOC fractions, carbonates, pH, etc.) and validate the predictions with data from Year 2 and Year 3 (i.e., two and three years after the implementation of CFPs). This exercise will be done in detail in Task 4.4 Modeling of future trends of carbon sequestration and Task 4.5 Data interpretation, reporting and verification. In addition to process-based models, hybrid modelling approaches that combine DSM, remote sensing (e.g., Sentinel-2 products), and SOC measurements can be explored for perennial systems with high variability in aboveground biomass and complex canopy structures like orchards (e.g., avocado plantations) or dehesa/montado systems.

4.5 Establishment of baseline SOC values

LILAS4SOILS does not have among its main objectives to develop methods for establishment of baselines for carbon farming MRV. By baseline, we refer here to “the carbon removals (and potentially emissions) that would have occurred in absence of the carbon removal project” (Gómez-Giménez et al., 2024). Since at LILAS4SOILS we will sample and estimate the mean SOC stock at 0-30 cm at each farm before the implementation of CFPs, it would be straightforward to set specific static baselines with the measure and remeasure approach (e.g., baseline is assumed to be 0 Mg C ha⁻¹). A specific baseline is that with data characterizing the farm or field from the carbon farming project, whereas a static (or ex ante) baseline is that measured only once during the duration of the project (Ruysschaert et al., 2024). In addition, at some farms we might be able to set control sites where the management is not modified by the introduction of (new) CFPs. Hence, we can set specific dynamic baselines, i.e., the baseline is modified during the development of the carbon farming project or established at the end. However, we note that the re-evaluation of baselines is suggested not to take place at least five years after entering the carbon farming

project (Gómez-Giménez et al., 2024). Specific baselines can also be estimated with the ARMOSA model assuming business as usual management plans.

The identification and monitoring of control sites near the intervention areas may not be possible in some cases because the agricultural management in the region is predominantly of regenerative agriculture, or due to limited funding. Specific static baselines may be then preferred. Legacy SOC data in similar crop systems and at similar local pedoclimatic conditions can be used to estimate a baseline. There are several methods for setting initial values of SOC stocks (or baseline SOC) for a particular land use and pedoclimatic context, which generally rely on similarity metrics for soil-forming factors and soil properties between the area of interest and its neighbouring region. DSM frameworks and concepts like genoforms and phenoforms (Rossiter and Bouma, 2018) and their analogous genosoils and phenosoils (Huang et al., 2018), digital terron mapping (Carré and McBratney, 2005; Malone et al., 2014), pedogenon mapping (Román Dobarco et al., 2021), or homosols (Mallavan et al., 2010; Nenkam et al., 2023) can be useful for these situations. These DSM frameworks have in common that the soil-forming factors and soil properties are represented by spatially exhaustive covariates (e.g., digital elevation models and derived terrain attributes, lithology maps, climate gridded data, etc.) as per the *scorpan* model (McBratney et al., 2003). *Scorpan* models establish quantitative relationships between soil properties or soil classes (response variables) and seven predictive factors: other soil properties (*s*), climate (*c*), organisms (*o*), relief (*r*), parent material (*p*), time (*a*) and spatial position (*n*).

Pedogenon maps define classes with homogeneous soil-forming factors for a given reference time (i.e., temporal baseline) applying unsupervised classification to a set of quantitative regionalised covariates. The underlying assumption is that within each class the long-term pedogenetic processes are similar and hence would result in similar soil capacity to store SOC and similar resilience to management and land use history. Maps of pedogenon classes can be defined from local (Jang et al., 2022) to continental scale (Román Dobarco et al., 2023). Then, they can be combined with high-resolution spatial data on land use (e.g., CORINE Land Cover at 100 m (European Environment Agency, 2019), CLCplus Backbone at 10 m (European Environment Agency, 2024)) to derive subclasses where we assume similar inherent capacity and pedogenesis, but substantial differences in soil properties and functions due to management history, i.e., *phenosoils*. Pedogenon, genosoil, and phenosoil maps have been used to assess the change in SOC stock at local scale linked to agricultural activities and set SOC sequestration potential (Jang et al., 2023), and more recently to assess SOC dynamics at continental scale (Styc et al., 2025). Thus, pedogenon and phenosoils maps can be populated with SOC legacy data from public national, European or global soil datasets (e.g., LUCAS (Orgiazzi et al., 2018), Carbosol (Llorente et al., 2018), IGCS (Inventaire, Gestion et Conservation des Sols)(Arrouays et al., 2004), etc.) ongoing projects (e.g., BENCHMARKS, AI4SOILHEALTH, MARVIC) and targeted sampling to set baseline levels by phenosoil class. Baseline levels of SOC content and stocks for each phenosoil can be determined from the distribution of available SOC data (e.g., median SOC stocks, inter-quantile range) and used for their respective demo sites. This approach is more similar to the methods for standardised baseline by MARVIC (Ruysschaert et al., 2024) and MRV4SOC projects (Gómez-Giménez et al., 2024), that consider environmental zones and pedoclimatic. Specifically, the phenosoil approach is more comparable to one approach suggested by MRV4SOC where standard baselines are defined as the common practices from a region using available datasets, observational data (LUCAS/ Copernicus) and digital soil maps. This approach has the disadvantage that the error of DSM maps might be greater than the desired carbon removal range.

Digital terron maps are also created applying unsupervised classification models (e.g., k-means, fuzzy clustering) to landscape attributes and soil property maps (e.g., clay, pH, mineralogy) to define soil-landscape units that can be used for land capability assessment or agricultural management zones, often

with emphasis on vineyards as per the terroir concept (Malone et al., 2014). Similarly, digital terrain maps developed at local or regional scale and combined with legacy soil datasets and land use can be used as strata for setting up baselines of SOC stocks for the local (or regional) pedoclimatic and landscape conditions. The concept of homosols can be useful for areas with sparse soil data, by identifying areas of the world that have similar soils and may have available soil data. The baseline SOC stocks for specific land uses or agricultural systems by homosols type can be transferred to geographically distant areas with the same homosols.

It is possible that a demo site or intervention area is located over several phenosols, terrain classes, or soil types (World Reference Base system of soil classification (WRB, 2022)), if there is high heterogeneity of soil characteristics within the intervention area. The intra-site variability may have been captured by the stratification based on environmental covariates. Baseline SOC stocks identified for the local or regional pedoclimatic and landscape condition can be used as input for modelling the trend for BAU scenario with a hybrid approach and propagate uncertainty.

4.6 Available resources on sampling design and implementation in R

In Annex A we provide a tutorial for conducting the sampling design using R. We assume that the user is familiar with using R and has some notions of spatial analysis. Providing an introduction to R is beyond the scope of this protocol, but we indicate some available resources for beginners:

RStudio Education has a blog post with several resources for beginning learning R (<https://education.rstudio.com/learn/beginner/>). Among the resources they suggest, we highlight the following:

- The Basic Basics lesson by R Ladies Sydney (<https://rldiessydney.org/courses/01-basicbasics-0>).
- The one-hour webinar by Thomas Mock “A Gentle Introduction to Tidy Statistics in R” (<https://posit.co/resources/videos/a-gentle-introduction-to-tidy-statistics-in-r/>).
- The web book “Hands-On Programming with R” by Garrett Grolemund ([Hands-On Programming with R](#)), and the web book by “R for Data Science” (<https://r4ds.hadley.nz/>) by Hadley Wickham, Mine Çetinkaya-Rundel, and Garrett Grolemund.

There are many other introduction courses to R that can be found in internet, like the web book “An introduction to R” (<https://intro2r.com/>) by Alex Douglas and co-authors.

Once the user is more comfortable using R, there are several resources for learning spatial analysis and geocomputation with R. For example:

- The web book “Using Spatial Data with R” by Claudia A. Engel (<https://cengel.github.io/R-spatial/>).
- The second edition of the book “Geocomputation with R” by Robin Lovelace, Jakub Nowosad, and Jannes Muenchow (<https://r.geocompx.org/>).

And several resources are more specific for the sampling approaches that we apply in Annex A:

- Tutorial by David Rossiter on using the package *spcosa* in R for stratified random sampling using compact geographical strata (https://www.css.cornell.edu/faculty/dgr2/ static/files/R_html/SpatialCoverageSampling_Tutorial.html).

- Tutorial on how to implement *conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling* (cLHS) with R by Dave White (2018) (NRCS, USDA) (<https://ncss-tech.github.io/soil-pit/sandbox/dave/clhs.html>).
- Online book by the Soil Survey Staff (31/01/2025) “Statistics for Soil Survey” (NRCS and National Cooperative Soil Survey) (https://ncss-tech.github.io/stats_for_soil_survey/book/). With a chapter dedicated to different spatial sampling strategies and their implementation in R (https://ncss-tech.github.io/stats_for_soil_survey/book/sampling.html#sampling-strategies).
- Online book by Dick Brus (2023) “Spatial Sampling with R” (<https://dickbrus.github.io/SpatialSamplingwithR/>).
- Online book by Richard Arnold et al. (2025) on “Sample Survey” for the course STAT 392 at the Victoria University of Wellington and at Statistics New Zealand (<https://homepages.ecs.vuw.ac.nz/~rarnold/STAT392/SampleSurveysBook/book/>).

There are several self-paced tutorials for learning Google Earth Engine (GEE) (<https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/tutorials/tutorials>). GEE is freely available for non-commercial uses, such as research projects. However, learning GEE with a guided course, and a teacher that can solve doubts is recommended based on our own experience.

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Annex A

Applying the soil sampling protocol with R

Sampling design by Stolbovoy et al (2007)

The first step is to install the packages that we will use to run the script. If you don't have R and RStudio installed in your computer, you can do it following this link: <https://posit.co/download/rstudio-desktop/>

```
install.packages(c('readr', 'sf', 'terra', 'leaflet', 'tidyverse', 'units'))
```

Once the packages we will use are installed, we load them into the R session.

```
library(readr)
library(sf)
library(terra)
library(tidyverse)
library(units)
```

We will set our working directory. This is the folder where we will store the output of the script. Change the path to a directory at your computer. In my case:

```
setwd("~/LILAS4SOIL/RScripts/tutorial")
```

We will load the shapefile with the boundaries of our study area (the field, pasture, vineyard, or orchard that we want to monitor for SOC change. for this, we use the sf package for spatial features. change the path and name of your shapefile. We use the field at Behialde as in the previous examples. The object tells us that the Coordinate reference system is ETRS89 / UTM zone 30N.

```
polygon <- sf::st_read("0:/Cambio
Climatico/SUELOS_SOC_STOLBOVOY/2024_Behialde_LILAS4SOILS/Behialde_04_GL_aukera1.shp")
## Reading layer `Behialde_04_GL_aukera1' from data source
##   `0:\Cambio
Climatico\SUELOS_SOC_STOLBOVOY\2024_Behialde_LILAS4SOILS\Behialde_04_GL_aukera1.shp'
##   using driver `ESRI Shapefile'
## Simple feature collection with 1 feature and 22 fields
## Geometry type: POLYGON
## Dimension:      XY
## Bounding box:  xmin: 531393.4 ymin: 4763591 xmax: 531678.4 ymax: 4763786
## Projected CRS: ETRS89 / UTM zone 30N
```

We can measure the area as well with the package units, in hectares.

```
field_area <- sf::st_area(polygon)
my_area <- sum(units::set_units(field_area, ha),na.rm=TRUE)
## Area in hectares
my_area

## 2.723046 [ha]
```

Load a custom R function to create the sampling design at any study area.

```
source("~/LILAS4SOIL/RScripts/tutorial/stolbovoy_function.R")
```

Apply this function to your study area. Here I named “polygon” my study area, and I use it as input for the function for the option “field_shp”. You need to specify the EPSG code of your zone as input for “crs_t”. We will be working with a projected CRS. For example, for the Basque Country (Spain) we use the EPSG:25830 (ETRS89 / UTM zone 30N) (<https://spatialreference.org/ref/epsg/25830/>). The coordinates that we will use with the GPS to locate the sampling points at the field will use this CRS, so it is important that we set it right. Finally, we need to specify the number of cells that we want to sample. We use the recommendations by Stolbovoy et al. (2007) of three sampling units for a study area between 1-5 ha.

```
Stolbovoy_test <- stolbovoy_sf_function(field_shp = polygon,
                                       Ncells = 3,
                                       crs_t = 25830)
```

We can examine several outputs. They are stored as elements of a list in Stolbovoy_test. First, if we want to visualize the location of the study area with satellite imagery.

```
Stolbovoy_test$field_map
```


If we want to visualize the grid, and how the numbers vary from 0-100 (with a continuous palette. The darker colours correspond to the grid cells with lower numbers.)

```
Stolbovoy_test$grid_map
```


Next, if you want to see the selected cells.

Stolbovoy_test\$stolbovoy_map

and the sampling points (25 points in this example).

```
Stolbovoy_test$stolbovoy_points
```


There is a table called “summary_table” that summarizes the information, indicating the coordinates (X, Y), the number of the grid cell, the type of point, “centroid”, “vertex”, or “sampling point”, and the distance between sampling points (Gs/6).

```
summary_table <- Stolbovoy_test$summary_table
```

To see the first 10 observations of the table

```
summary_table[1:10,]
```

##	X	Y	Grid_Cell	type	dist_sampling_points
## 1	531493.2	4763719	1	centroid	NA
## 2	531493.2	4763634	11	centroid	NA
## 3	531578.6	4763691	17	centroid	NA
## 4	531478.9	4763705	1	vertex	NA
## 5	531507.4	4763705	1	vertex	NA
## 6	531507.4	4763733	1	vertex	NA
## 7	531478.9	4763733	1	vertex	NA
## 8	531478.9	4763619	11	vertex	NA
## 9	531507.4	4763619	11	vertex	NA
## 10	531507.4	4763648	11	vertex	NA

```
write_excel_csv(x = summary_table, file = "summary_table.csv", col_names = TRUE,
delim = ";")
```

We can export it into a csv file.

```
write_excel_csv(x = summary_table, file = "summary_table.csv", col_names = TRUE,
delim = ";")
```

You can further export the vertices into a shapefile accessing “Stolbovoy_test\$Selection_Stolbovoy” and open it with other GIS software (ArcGIS, QGIS, etc.).

```
st_write(Stolbovoy_test$Selection_Stolbovoy,
  append=FALSE,
  dsn = "Selection_Stolbovoy.shp",
  driver = "ESRI Shapefile")

## Writing layer `Selection_Stolbovoy' to data source
## `Selection_Stolbovoy.shp' using driver `ESRI Shapefile'
## Writing 3 features with 1 fields and geometry type Polygon.
```

We can also access and export the sampling points within each cell individually at “Stolbovoy_test\$coordinates_Sampling_points”. The third column of this table gives the grid cell number.

```
sampling_points <- Stolbovoy_test$coordinates_Sampling_points

head(sampling_points)

##           X           Y Grid_Cell           type dist_sampling_points
## 1 531493.2 4763719           1 sampling point           4.749121
## 2 531497.9 4763719           1 sampling point           4.749121
## 3 531502.7 4763719           1 sampling point           4.749121
## 4 531488.4 4763719           1 sampling point           4.749121
## 5 531483.7 4763719           1 sampling point           4.749121
## 6 531497.9 4763724           1 sampling point           4.749121

write_excel_csv(x = sampling_points, file = "sampling_points.csv", col_names = TRUE,
delim = ";")
```

If we want them as shapefile, we can transform them into a spatial object and export. Again, you need to substitute in the following code the appropriate EPSG code for your zone. At “dsn” we specify the destination. You can give here the name of the file to save the sampling points and the path to your directory.

```
sampling_points_sf <- sampling_points %>%
  st_as_sf(coords = c("X", "Y"), crs = 25830)

st_write(sampling_points_sf,
  append=FALSE,
```

```

    dsn = "sampling_points.shp",
    driver = "ESRI Shapefile")

## Warning in abbreviate_shapefile_names(obj): Field names abbreviated for ESRI
## Shapefile driver

## Deleting layer `sampling_points' using driver `ESRI Shapefile'
## Writing layer `sampling_points' to data source
## `sampling_points.shp' using driver `ESRI Shapefile'
## Writing 75 features with 3 fields and geometry type Point.

```

If you also want to export the grid and explore it with another GIS software

```

st_write(Stolbovoy_test$grid,
  append=FALSE,
  dsn="stolbovoy_grid.shp",
  driver = "ESRI Shapefile")

## Writing layer `stolbovoy_grid' to data source
## `stolbovoy_grid.shp' using driver `ESRI Shapefile'
## Writing 100 features with 1 fields and geometry type Polygon.

```

Stratified random sampling from compact geographical strata

We will create compact geostrata using the tutorial found at <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/spcosa/vignettes/spcosa.html> (Walvoort et al., 2023). Before using the package `spcosa` make sure you have Java installed at your computer with the version compatible with your computer. Install the packages `rJava` and `spcosa` and load them.

```

install.packages(c('rJava', 'spcosa'))
library(rJava)
library(spcosa)

## Warning: package 'spcosa' was built under R version 4.4.3

```

The study area should be in UTM projection. We can project it if it is not. We also transform the simple feature (package `sf`) into a spatial object (package `sp`), which works with `spcosa`.

```

polygon_utm <- st_transform(polygon, 25830)
### Transform to spatial
field_sp <- as_Spatial(polygon_utm)

```

In the case of LILAS4SOILS, we can adapt the protocol by Arrouays et al (2018) placing two sampling plots per strata, and only 3 strata instead of 20. We start by dividing the study area into equal-area compact geostrata. The number of strata is set with `nStrata = 3`. We set the seed to a number of our choice, to ensure reproducibility. We can tell the function the number of initializations that we want

to do ($nTry = 10$), and the function returns the best result. The number of grid cells into which is divided the study area is controlled with `nGridCells`. Higher value of `nGridCells` results in higher resolution for our strata. This step can take some time.

```
set.seed(3354)
stratification <- stratify(field_sp,
  nStrata = 3,
  equalArea = TRUE,
  nTry = 10,
  nGridCells = 20000)
```

We can plot the resulting strata

```
plot(stratification) +
  scale_x_continuous(name = "Easting (m)") +
  scale_y_continuous(name = "Northing (m)")

## Scale for x is already present.
## Adding another scale for x, which will replace the existing scale.
## Scale for y is already present.
## Adding another scale for y, which will replace the existing scale.
```


The next step will place randomly six sampling units in total. We can decide to locate more than one sampling unit per stratum, e.g., two units per stratum is set with $n = 2$. By changing the number within `set.seed()` we generate a different random sampling.

```
set.seed(546)
sampling_pattern <- spsample(stratification, n = 2)
plot(stratification, sampling_pattern)+
  ggplot2::scale_x_continuous(name = "Easting (m)") +
  ggplot2::scale_y_continuous(name = "Northing (m)")

## Scale for x is already present.
## Adding another scale for x, which will replace the existing scale.
## Scale for y is already present.
## Adding another scale for y, which will replace the existing scale.
```



```
set.seed(943)
sampling_pattern <- spsample(stratification, n = 2)
plot(stratification, sampling_pattern)+
  ggplot2::scale_x_continuous(name = "Easting (m)") +
  ggplot2::scale_y_continuous(name = "Northing (m)")

## Scale for x is already present.
## Adding another scale for x, which will replace the existing scale.
## Scale for y is already present.
## Adding another scale for y, which will replace the existing scale.
```


We need to extract the coordinates of the sampling points and create a multipoint object.

```
#getNumberOfStrata(stratification)
```

```
sampling_points <- as(sampling_pattern, "data.frame")
```

```
### Create multipoint
```

```
points_sf <- sf::st_multipoint(x = as.matrix(sampling_points), dim = "XYZ")
```

```
points_sf <- sf::st_sfc(points_sf, crs = 25830)
```

```
colnames(sampling_points) <- c("X", "Y")
```

```
sampling_points
```

```
##           X           Y  
## 1 531573.5 4763768  
## 2 531612.1 4763718  
## 3 531487.5 4763744  
## 4 531492.2 4763702  
## 5 531463.3 4763664  
## 6 531456.3 4763636
```

We can also visualize how would a 4 m radius plot look like, creating a buffer of 4 m around the centre of the sampling unit. We can use this to see if the sampling units overlap the boundaries of the strata or among themselves.

```
### Create buffer. Let's see if they overlap
sampling_plots <- st_buffer(points_sf, dist = 5)
#plot(sampling_plots)

### Create buffer. Let's see if they overlap
sampling_plots_wgs84 <- st_transform(sampling_plots, crs = 4326)
polygon_wgs_84 <- st_transform(polygon, crs = 4326)

leaflet(sampling_plots_wgs84) %>%
  addTiles() %>%
  addProviderTiles('Esri.WorldImagery') %>%
  addPolygons(color = "#d19a1a",
              fillColor = "#d19a1a",
              weight =4,
              opacity = 0.3,
              group="Sampling plots") %>%
  addPolygons(data=polygon_wgs_84,
              color = "#cd5c5c",
              fillColor = "transparent",
              weight =2,
              opacity = 1,
              group="polygon") %>%
  addScaleBar(
    position = "bottomright",
    options = scaleBarOptions(metric=TRUE, imperial =FALSE, maxWidth = 200)
  )
```


In the previous example, two plots overlap with the boundaries of the study area. We generate the second sampling by changing the seed,

```
set.seed(665)
sampling_pattern <- spsample(stratification, n = 2)
sampling_points <- as(sampling_pattern, "data.frame")

### Create multipoint
points_sf <- st_multipoint(x = as.matrix(sampling_points), dim = "XYZ")
points_sf <- st_sfc(points_sf, crs = 25830)

### Create buffer. Let's see if they overlap
sampling_plots <- st_buffer(points_sf, dist = 5)
#plot(sampling_plots)

### Create buffer. Let's see if they overlap
sampling_plots_wgs84 <- st_transform(sampling_plots, crs = 4326)
polygon_wgs_84 <- st_transform(polygon, crs = 4326)

leaflet(sampling_plots_wgs84) %>%
  addTiles() %>%
  addProviderTiles('Esri.WorldImagery') %>%
  addPolygons(color = "#d19a1a",
             fillColor = "#d19a1a",
```

```

    weight =4,
    opacity = 0.3,
    group="Sampling plots") %>%
addPolygons(data=polygon_wgs_84,
  color = "#cd5c5c",
  fillColor = "transparent",
  weight =2,
  opacity = 1,
  group="polygon") %>%
addScaleBar(
  position = "bottomright",
  options = scaleBarOptions(metric=TRUE, imperial =FALSE, maxWidth = 200)
)

```


Stratified random sampling from strata created from environmental covariates

This method starts by loading the layers with the ancillary data of environmental covariates. We start with the NDVI layers created in Google Earth Engine. We assume that for your demo site you have previously created or compiled the environmental covariates.

```

### Load the Sentinel-2 NDVI indices
library(terra)

```

```

ndvi_dir <- "C:/Users/mroman/OneDrive - Neiker,
S.A/Documentos/LILAS4SOIL/Covariates/Behialde/"

ndvi_q1 <- terra::rast(paste0(ndvi_dir,"NDVIq1_median.tif"))
ndvi_q2 <- terra::rast(paste0(ndvi_dir,"NDVIq2_median.tif"))
ndvi_q3 <- terra::rast(paste0(ndvi_dir,"NDVIq3_median.tif"))
ndvi_q4 <- terra::rast(paste0(ndvi_dir,"NDVIq4_median.tif"))
ndvi_sd <- terra::rast(paste0(ndvi_dir,"NDVI_sd.tif"))

ndvi <- c(ndvi_q1, ndvi_q2, ndvi_q3, ndvi_q4, ndvi_sd)
names(ndvi) <- c("ndvi_q1", "ndvi_q2", "ndvi_q3", "ndvi_q4", "ndvi_sd")

```

The spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 is around 10 m. We load the relief derivatives with the terra package. Candidate covariates for stratification are elevation, slope, easternness, northerness, the product of slope by northerness, topographic wetness index (TWI), and mid slope position.

```

### Load slope, DEM, northness, etc... Relief
relief_dir <- "C:/Users/mroman/OneDrive - Neiker,
S.A/Documentos/LILAS4SOIL/Covariates/Euskadi/Relief/"
dem <- terra::rast(paste0(relief_dir,"mdt_lidar_2017_25m_etrs89.tif"))
slope <- terra::rast(paste0(relief_dir,"slope.tif"))
northerness <- terra::rast(paste0(relief_dir,"northerness.tif"))
easterness <- terra::rast(paste0(relief_dir,"easterness.tif"))
nor_slope <- terra::rast(paste0(relief_dir,"nor_slope.tif"))
twi <- terra::rast(paste0(relief_dir,"twi_saga.tif"))
mid_slope <- terra::rast(paste0(relief_dir,"mid_slope.tif"))
r <- c(dem, slope, northerness, easterness, nor_slope, mid_slope, twi)

## Warning: [rast] CRS do not match

names(r) <- c("elevation", "slope", "northerness", "easterness", "nor_slope",
"mid_slope", "twi")
plot(r)

```


These layers are available for the whole of Euskadi. Now we process the covariates so that all have the same resolution, CRS and extent. The NDVI layers are in EPSG:4326, we project them to EPSG:25830 with bilinear resampling because they are continuous variables.

```
### Resample the NDVI layers to EPSG 25830
ndvi_utm30N <- terra::project(ndvi, "EPSG:25830", method="bilinear")
```

The relief covariates are cropped to the extent of the pasture, our study area at Behialde. We resample them to the same extent as the Sentinel-2 NDVI layer, and create a mask, making NA the cells outside the study area.

```
### Crop and resample the relief variables to the same extent and resolution
r_Behialde <- terra::crop(r, ndvi_utm30N)
r_Behialde <- terra::resample(r_Behialde, ndvi_utm30N, method="bilinear")

mask_fun <- function(x) {ifelse(is.na(x), NA, 1)}
mask_Behialde <- app(ndvi_utm30N[[1]], mask_fun)

covars <- c(ndvi_utm30N, r_Behialde)

## Warning: [rast] CRS do not match

covars_behialde <- mask(covars, mask_Behialde)
names(covars_behialde) <- c("ndvi_q1", "ndvi_q2", "ndvi_q3", "ndvi_q4", "ndvi_sd",
```

```
"elevation", "slope", "northness", "eastness",
"nor_slope", "mid_slope", "twi")
```

```
plot(covars_behialde)
```


After visual examination of the covariates at Behialde, I decided to use elevation, slope, the product of northerness by slope, and TWI together with the NDVI variables, and mask the pixels that fall outside the boundaries of the pasture.

```
### Elevation, slope, northness x slope, TWI
input_c <- subset(covars_behialde,c("ndvi_q1", "ndvi_q2", "ndvi_q3", "ndvi_q4",
"ndvi_sd", "elevation", "slope", "nor_slope", "twi"))

### Use only pixels that fall within the boundaries
input_c <- terra::mask(input_c, polygon)
```

Before doing k-means clustering, we perform the inverse Cholesky transformation. This transformation decorrelates the data and as a result, the Euclidean distance calculated on the decorrelated variables is equivalent to the Mahalanobis distance calculated on the original variables. First we scale the variables, transform the raster layers into a data frame, and keep the coordinates.

Scale variables

```
input_s <- scale(input_c, center = TRUE, scale = TRUE)
input_df <- as.data.frame(input_s, xy=TRUE)
input_df_coords <- input_df[,1:2]
```

Now we apply the inverse Cholesky transformation with matrix algebra.

Apply the inverse Cholesky transformation

```
C <- chol(var(as.matrix(input_df[,3:ncol(input_df)])))
input_df.rs <- as.matrix(input_df[,3:ncol(input_df)]) %%% solve(C)
```

I do some preliminary analyses to select the optimal number of clusters. We have said that the minimum would be around 3. But this needs to be checked on a case-by-case basis. The package Nbclust offers calculating many internal clustering quality indices. By saying index = "all" we calculate all available indices. You can change the index to see the results for Silhouette, Dunn, or your preferred index. The input data is the data frame with the rescaled covariate data, input_df.rs. We apply k-means clustering. We will test between 2 to 6 clusters.

I apply the function NBCLust to select the optimal number of clusters

```
library(NbClust)
set.seed(2233)
res <- NbClust::NbClust(input_df.rs,
  distance = "euclidean",
  min.nc=2, max.nc=6,
  method = "kmeans",
  index = "all")

## *****
## * Among all indices:
## * 7 proposed 2 as the best number of clusters
## * 2 proposed 3 as the best number of clusters
## * 2 proposed 4 as the best number of clusters
## * 3 proposed 5 as the best number of clusters
## * 10 proposed 6 as the best number of clusters
##
##          ***** Conclusion *****
##
## * According to the majority rule, the best number of clusters is 6
##
## *****
```

The Dunn index suggests 2 clusters as the optimal. The Silhouette and the Calinski-Harabasz suggest 6 clusters as optimal. With the package ClusterR and the function KMeans_rcpp we perform clustering for n=2,3,6.

```
library(ClusterR)
```

```
## Warning: package 'ClusterR' was built under R version 4.4.3
```

```
set.seed(1990)
kmeans_2 <- ClusterR::KMeans_rcpp(input_df.rs,
                                  clusters = 2,
                                  num_init = 10,
                                  max_iters = 5000,
                                  fuzzy = FALSE,
                                  initializer = 'kmeans++',
                                  verbose = F)

set.seed(1995)
kmeans_3 <- ClusterR::KMeans_rcpp(input_df.rs,
                                  clusters = 3,
                                  num_init = 10,
                                  max_iters = 5000,
                                  fuzzy = FALSE,
                                  initializer = 'kmeans++',
                                  verbose = F)

set.seed(1984)
kmeans_6 <- ClusterR::KMeans_rcpp(input_df.rs,
                                  clusters = 6,
                                  num_init = 10,
                                  max_iters = 5000,
                                  fuzzy = FALSE,
                                  initializer = 'kmeans++',
                                  verbose = F)
```

Now that we have created different stratifications, we map them applying the function `predict_KMeans` to the rescaled raster layers.

```
strata_map <- function(input_s, kmeans_model){

  ### Map strata
  ### Transform into a dataframe
  tile.df <- as.data.frame(input_s, row.names=NULL, optional=FALSE, xy=TRUE,
                           na.rm=FALSE)

  ### For each new pixel, I first have to rescale its values
  ## Take out the coordinates
  tile.df.coords <- tile.df[,1:2]
  tile.df <- tile.df[,3:ncol(tile.df)]

  # Rescale the data with CLORPT.df (sample from the stack covariates that was used to
  # calibrate the kmeans in the first place)
  tile.df.rs <- as.matrix(tile.df) %*% solve(C)
  tile.df.rs <- as.data.frame(tile.df.rs)

  ### Predict cluster assignment
```

```

### Extract the index of the dataframe rows that are na/nan/Inf
df.na <- which(apply(tile.df.rs, MARGIN = 1, FUN = function(x) {any(is.na(x))}))

### Create empty prediction column
tile.df.rs$cluster <- NA

### If K is more than one instead of km.pedogenon.rcpp being a kmeans model, it would be a list of models
### km.pedogenon.rcpp[[m]]$centroids
### predict in those rows where there are not na
tile.df.rs[-df.na, ]$cluster <- ClusterR::predict_KMeans(data = tile.df.rs[-df.na,1:(ncol(tile.df.rs)-1)],
                                                         CENTROIDS =
kmeans_model$centroids)
### Assign the values to a new raster
k.pred <- setValues(input_s[[1]], tile.df.rs$cluster)
names(k.pred) <- "Strata"
return(k.pred) # Return this
}

strata2 <- strata_map(input_s, kmeans_model = kmeans_2)
strata3 <- strata_map(input_s, kmeans_model = kmeans_3)
strata6 <- strata_map(input_s, kmeans_model = kmeans_6)

```

Now we can visualize the strata with leaflet. For that, we resample the layers to EPSG:4326 first.

```

### Plot with Leaflet
library(leaflet)

#### Visualization
behalde_wgs84 <- sf::st_transform(polygon, 4326)
strata2_wgs84 <- terra::project(strata2, "EPSG:4326", method="near")
strata3_wgs84 <- terra::project(strata3, "EPSG:4326", method="near")
strata6_wgs84 <- terra::project(strata6, "EPSG:4326", method="near")

levels(strata2_wgs84) <- data.frame(id=1:2, strata=c("1", "2"))
levels(strata3_wgs84) <- data.frame(id=1:3, strata=c("1", "2", "3"))
levels(strata6_wgs84) <- data.frame(id=1:6, strata=c("1", "2", "3", "4", "5", "6"))

library(leaflet)
library(terra)
library(sf)
library(viridisLite)

## Warning: package 'viridisLite' was built under R version 4.4.3

# Define color palette
pal2 <- colorFactor(palette = viridisLite::viridis(2),
                   domain = terra::values(strata2_wgs84),
                   na.color = "transparent")

```

```

leaflet(behialde_wgs84) %>%
  addTiles() %>%
  addProviderTiles('Esri.WorldImagery') %>%
  addPolygons(color = "red",
              fillColor = "transparent",
              weight = 3,
              opacity = 1) %>%
  addScaleBar(position = "bottomright",
              options = scaleBarOptions(metric=TRUE, imperial =FALSE, maxWidth =
200)) %>%
  addRasterImage(strata2_wgs84,
                 project = FALSE,
                 colors = pal2,
                 opacity = 0.8) %>%
  addLegend(pal = pal2,
            values = values(strata2_wgs84),
            title = "Strata")

```



```

pal3 <- colorFactor(palette = viridisLite::viridis(3),
                    domain = terra::values(strata3_wgs84),
                    na.color = "transparent")

```



```
leaflet(behialde_wgs84) %>%
  addTiles() %>%
  addProviderTiles('Esri.WorldImagery') %>%
  addPolygons(color = "red",
              fillColor = "transparent",
              weight = 3,
              opacity = 1) %>%
  addScaleBar(position = "bottomright",
              options = scaleBarOptions(metric=TRUE, imperial =FALSE, maxWidth =
200)) %>%
  addRasterImage(strata3_wgs84,
                 project = FALSE,
                 colors = pal3,
                 opacity = 0.8) %>%
  addLegend(pal = pal3,
            values = values(strata3_wgs84),
            title = "Strata")
```



```
pal6 <- colorFactor(palette = viridisLite::viridis(6),
                    domain = terra::values(strata6_wgs84),
                    na.color = "transparent")
```

```
leaflet(behialde_wgs84) %>%  
  addTiles() %>%  
  addProviderTiles('Esri.WorldImagery') %>%  
  addPolygons(color = "red",  
             fillColor = "transparent",  
             weight = 3,  
             opacity = 1) %>%  
  addScaleBar(position = "bottomright",  
             options = scaleBarOptions(metric=TRUE, imperial =FALSE, maxWidth =  
200)) %>%  
  addRasterImage(strata6_wgs84,  
                project = FALSE,  
                colors = pal6,  
                opacity = 0.8) %>%  
  addLegend(pal = pal6,  
            values = values(strata6_wgs84),  
            title = "Strata")
```


After visual comparison of the different stratification, we decide to use two strata at Behialde.

Proportional allocation of soil samples to strata

We will assign the number of samples to each stratum proportionally to the area they occupy. With a quick script, we see that stratum 1 would get approximately two thirds of the samples by the study area whereas stratum 2 would get one third. The stratification with three strata with proportional allocation would assign 19%, 72%, and 9% of samples to strata 1, 2, and 3 respectively.

```
### Transform the raster layer with the tw strata to a dataframe
library(tidyverse)
library(dplyr)

area_2 <- as.data.frame(strata2)

n_sample <- area_2 %>%
  group_by(Strata) %>%
  summarise(., sample_perc = round(n()/nrow(area_2)*100,digits=1))

n_sample

## # A tibble: 2 × 2
##   Strata sample_perc
##   <dbl>     <dbl>
## 1     1         66.9
## 2     2         33.1

area_3 <- as.data.frame(strata3)

n_sample_3 <- area_3 %>%
  group_by(Strata) %>%
  summarise(., sample_perc = round(n()/nrow(area_3)*100,digits=1))

n_sample_3

## # A tibble: 3 × 2
##   Strata sample_perc
##   <dbl>     <dbl>
## 1     1         18.9
## 2     2         72
## 3     3          9.1
```

How can I take 2 random samples in strata 1 and one random sample in strata 2?

Let's say that we have budget for 6 sampling units, that would result in 4 sampling units at stratum 1 and 2 sampling units at stratum 2. We can allocate a random sampling with the function `strata` from package `sampling`. There are many other packages that allow for simple random sampling or stratified random sampling with R. The code was adapted from <https://dickbrus.github.io/SpatialSamplingwithR/STSI.html#STSI>

```
n_sample <- area_2 %>%
  group_by(Strata) %>%
```



```

summarise(., sample_perc = round(n()/nrow(area_2)*100,digits=1),
          n_sample = round(n()/nrow(area_2)*6,digits=0))

n_sample

## # A tibble: 2 × 3
##   Strata sample_perc n_sample
##   <dbl>     <dbl>     <dbl>
## 1     1         66.9         4
## 2     2         33.1         2

### Assign the sampling units with the sampling package
library(sampling)

## Warning: package 'sampling' was built under R version 4.4.3

### Transform to ata.frame
strata2_df <- as.data.frame(strata2,xy = TRUE, na.rm = TRUE)

### Order by strata number
strata2_df <- dplyr::arrange(strata2_df, Strata)

### Assign sampling units by strata (remember the dataframe has to be in order of
stratum value)
set.seed(55)
sampling_units <- sampling::strata(data=strata2_df, ### Dataframe with the
stratification data
                                stratanames = "Strata", ### Vector with the name of the strata variable
                                size = n_sample$n_sample, ### Vector with the sample size per strata
                                method = "srswor") # Simple random sampling without replacement

## Now with getdata we obtain the information (coordinates, stratum ID) of the
sampling units
# getdata(strata2_df, sampling_units)

### If we want to add more randomness in terms of coordinates (because we were
sampling from the center of the grid, but the real population is infinite).

StratifiedRandomSample <- getdata(strata2_df, sampling_units)%>%
  mutate(X = x %>% jitter(amount = res(strata2)[1] / 2),
         Y = y %>% jitter(amount = res(strata2)[2] / 2))

StratifiedRandomSample

##           x           y Strata ID_unit      Prob Stratum         X         Y
## 62 531557.2 4763715     1      62 0.01230769     1 531553.9 4763717
## 163 531533.1 4763666     1     163 0.01230769     1 531536.2 4763667
## 244 531541.2 4763642     1     244 0.01230769     1 531537.7 4763645
## 257 531452.7 4763634     1     257 0.01230769     1 531451.2 4763635
## 375 531452.7 4763723     2     375 0.01242236     2 531451.3 4763721
## 401 531460.8 4763706     2     401 0.01242236     2 531460.5 4763706

```

Visualization of sampling points

We plot the sampling points with leaflet. We can also make a buffer of 4 m radius to check if the plots overlap.

```
# Convert back to an sf object for spatial operations
sampled_points_sf <- st_as_sf(StratifiedRandomSample, coords = c("X", "Y"), crs =
"EPSG:25830")

sampled_points_wgs84 <- st_transform(sampled_points_sf, 4326)

### Plot it
leaflet(behialde_wgs84) %>%
  addTiles() %>%
  addProviderTiles('Esri.WorldImagery') %>%
  addPolygons(color = "red",
              fillColor = "transparent",
              weight = 3,
              opacity = 1) %>%
  addScaleBar(position = "bottomright",
              options = scaleBarOptions(metric=TRUE, imperial =FALSE, maxWidth =
200)) %>%
  addRasterImage(strata2_wgs84,
                 project = FALSE,
                 colors = pal2,
                 opacity = 0.8) %>%
  addLegend(pal = pal2,
            values = values(strata2_wgs84),
            title = "Strata") %>%
  addMarkers(data =sampled_points_wgs84)
```


Conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling

Taking the same environmental covariates that for k-means stratification, we will assign sampling units with cLH using the clhs package.

```
library(clhs)

## Warning: package 'clhs' was built under R version 4.4.3

covars_input_df <- as.data.frame(input_c, xy=TRUE, na.rm=TRUE)

set.seed(886)
res <- clhs(x = covars_input_df[,3:ncol(covars_input_df)],
            size = 6,
            iter = 50000, temp = 1, tdecrease = 0.95,
            length.cycle = 10, progress = FALSE, simple = FALSE)

behalde_CLH <- covars_input_df[res$index_samples, ]
```

The location of the cLHS. We set 6 sampling units, but we could have taken as many as desired by changing the input “size”.

```
# Convert back to an sf object for spatial operations
cLHS_points_sf <- st_as_sf(behialde_CLH, coords = c("x", "y"), crs = "EPSG:25830")

cLHS_points_wgs84 <- st_transform(cLHS_points_sf, 4326)

### Plot it
leaflet(behialde_wgs84) %>%
  addTiles() %>%
  addProviderTiles('Esri.WorldImagery') %>%
  addPolygons(color = "red",
             fillColor = "transparent",
             weight = 3,
             opacity = 1) %>%
  addScaleBar(position = "bottomright",
             options = scaleBarOptions(metric=TRUE, imperial =FALSE, maxWidth =
200)) %>%
  addMarkers(data =cLHS_points_wgs84)
```


Annex B

A. Stratified random sampling from geostrata

1st – Check you have all the required material (the day before)

Before leaving to the field, kindly check the needed materials/steps:

- Check all equipment is clean.
- Calibrate GPS and confirm coordinate system.
- Prepare field data sheets with site IDs and strata.
- Carry extra sample bags, labels, gloves, and marker pens.
- Label bags according to the nomenclature:

Arable lands: FarmID_Date_SampleNo_Depth

Montado: FarmID_Date_SampleNo_Depth_Canopy(In/Out)

Line perennial crops: FarmID_Date_SampleNo_Depth_Line (Row/Interrow)

- Check you have all the required material organized – composite samples

Item	Check
Tablet/map with theoretical coordinates of sampling units	
GPS	
Compass	
Flags/sticks	
Measuring tape of 4m at least	
Soil probe or soil auger with at least 30 cm	
Spade with a 20 cm blade	
Small spade	
Field knife with flat blade	
Stainless steel rings + cylinder holder device	
Rubber mallet	
Permanent marker	
Two labelled reclosable plastic bags per sampling unit	
Two labelled reclosable plastic bags per sampling unit for bulk density	
Disposable laboratory gloves	

Paper towels	
Box to store and transport the samples	
Cooler with ice packs to preserve samples	
Plastic container (bucket)	
Ethanol 70%	

Check you have all the required material organized – bulk density (excavation method)

Item	Check
Short level (20cm)	
Annular rigid template (15-20 cm diameter)	
Soup spoon or small gardening shovel	
Transparent, thin, waterproof bags	
Scissors	

Suggested additional material:

Sieves (2 mm) – for field pre-cleaning of coarse fragments.

Spray bottle with ethanol or water – for cleaning tools.

Flag poles or stakes – mark plot centres for revisits.

Notebook / pens / pencils – waterproof types preferred.

Scale (portable) – estimate soil weight per composite.

2nd - Before sampling, take records:

Parameter:	Notes:
Weather	
Soil conditions	
Evidence of recent agricultural practices	

Last recorded agricultural practice	
Thickness of organic horizon	
Have you taken pictures yet? Of what?	

3rd – Follow the steps bellow per plot (experimental and control plots)

- Ideally the material for collecting samples between sampling units is different/cleaned thoroughly to prevent cross-contamination
- Take at least 500-600g of composite sample

Sampling procedure per sampling unit composite sample:

#	Step	Sampling unit		
		1	2	3
1	Mark the centre of the circle with a stick/flag following the GPS coordinates. Record the real location of the centre of the plot			
2	From there, mark the composite sampling sites with sticks, crosswards in cardinal directions, in the 2m and 4m perimeter			
3	Remove the centre sample 50 cm away from the centre			
4	Using the auger, sample the composite samples using clockwise motions			
5	Retrieve the horizons the depths separately, between 0-10 cm and 10-30 cm, into corresponding pre-labelled bags			
6	Store the sample in a cooler with ice packs.			

Sampling procedure per sampling unit bulk density/coarse fragments sample and to analyse soil moisture at field water capacity (core method):

#	Step	Sampling unit		
		1	2	3

1	Remove organic horizon from centre of the plot, as well as stones larger than 6 cm			
2	Near the centre of the circle, dig a pit for bulk density and coarse fragments. Adapt size of the pit to conditions of the soil. Rake the first two cm of soil away.			
3	Press the cylinder into the 2-10 cm layer of soil until the end. Be careful not to press excessively.			
4	Dig four holes around the cylinder, carefully, 2-3 cm around the ring.			
5	Extract the core using a spade, preserving the soil clump on top of the cylinder opening.			
6	Remove excess soil using a knife and roots using scissors.			
7	If less than 10% of cylinder is empty, fill with removed soil. If more than 10% is missing, repeat the process			
8	To take the 10-30 cm sample, repeat the same steps for the sampling, after digging to a depth of 20 cm in the place where the first core was taken.			
9	Take additional cylinders at these depths to take the field water capacity and permanent wilting points			

5th – Check that you have all the necessary samples

B. Transect sampling for crops and agroforestry in alleys

1st – Check you have all the required material (the day before)

Before leaving to the field, kindly check the needed materials/steps:

- Check all equipment is clean.
- Calibrate GPS and confirm coordinate system.
- Extra batteries for the GPS.
- Prepare field data sheets with site IDs and strata.
- Carry extra sample bags, labels, gloves, and marker pens.
- Label bags according to the nomenclature:

Arable lands: FarmID_Date_SampleNo_Depth

Montado: FarmID_Date_SampleNo_Depth_Canopy(In/Out)

Line perennial crops: FarmID_Date_SampleNo_Depth_Line (Row/Interrow)

Check you have all the required material organized – composite samples

Item	Check
Tablet/map with theoretical coordinates of sampling units	
GPS	
Compass	
Flags/sticks	
Measuring tape of 4m at least	
Soil probe or soil auger with at least 30 cm	
Spade with a 20 cm blade	
Small spade	
Field knife with flat blade	
Stainless steel rings + cylinder holder device	
Rubber mallet	
Permanent marker	
Two labelled reclosable plastic bags per sampling unit	
Two labelled reclosable plastic bags per sampling unit for bulk density	
Disposable laboratory gloves	
Paper towels	
Box to store and transport the samples	
Cooler with ice packs to preserve samples	
Plastic container (bucket)	

Check you have all the required material organized – bulk density (excavation method)

Item	Check
Short level (20cm)	
Annular rigid template (15-20 cm diameter)	
Soup spoon or small gardening shovel	

Transparent, thin, waterproof bags	
Scissors	

Suggested additional material:

Sieves (2 mm) – for field pre-cleaning of coarse fragments.

Spray bottle with ethanol or water – for cleaning tools.

Flag poles or stakes – mark plot centres for revisits.

Notebook / pens / pencils – waterproof types preferred.

Scale (portable) – estimate soil weight per composite.

2nd - Before sampling, take records:

Parameter:	Notes:
Weather	
Soil conditions	
Evidence of recent agricultural practices	
Last recorded agricultural practice	
Thickness of organic horizon	
Have you taken pictures yet? Of what?	

3rd – Establish the rows and interrows that will be sampled

- Locate the tree row closest to the coordinates of the sampling unit.
- Establish an area for sampling that allows for the design as shown by the figures below and measure the distance between tree rows (L) and between the trees in the row (d).

L	L/2	L/4
d	d/2	d/4

- Define a transect in the tree row encompassing three trees. Use two flags to make the beginning and end of the transect. Collect 8 subsamples along the transect, at d/4 distance between them. Make a composite sample labelled as “row”.
- Define a zigzag transect the interrow located east of the row (if possible). Use four flags to make the beginning and end of the transect. Collect 4 subsamples at L/4 and 4 subsamples L/2 distance from the row. Make a composite sample labelled as “Interrow”. Mark with a flag the centre of the row transect for bulk density
- Mark with a flag the centre of zigzag transect at L/4 (see figure below), for bulk density sample.
- Register the coordinates of the beginning and end of the transect in the tree row.

Sampling Unit	Point	Latitude	Longitude
Unit 1	Beginning		
	End		
Unit 2	Beginning		
	End		
Unit 3	Beginning		
	End		

- Register the approximate area of the row and interrow sampling areas

Row (m²)

Interrow (m²)

4th – Follow the steps below per plot (experimental and control plots, if applicable)

- The material for collecting samples between sampling units is different/cleaned thoroughly to prevent cross-contamination
- Take at least 500-600g of composite sample

Sampling procedure per sampling unit composite sample:

#	Step	Sampling unit		
		1	2	3

1	Mark the beginning and end of the transects with a stick/flag following the GPS coordinates. Record the real location of the transects.			
2	Using the auger, sample the composite samples using clockwise motions			
3	Collect 8 subsamples in each transect and place in separate pre-labelled bags for the row and interrow			
4	Retrieve the horizons the depths separately, between 0-10 cm and 10-30 cm, into corresponding pre-labelled bags			
5	Store the sample in a cooler with ice packs.			

Sampling procedure per sampling unit bulk density/coarse fragments sample and to analyse soil moisture at field water capacity (core method):

#	Step	Sampling unit		
		1	2	3
1	At the marked sites at the center of the transects, remove organic horizon from, as well as stones larger than 6 cm			
2	Dig a pit for bulk density and coarse fragments. Adapt size of the pit to conditions of the soil. Rake the first two cm of soil away.			
3	Press the cylinder into the 2-10 cm layer of soil until the end. Be careful not to press excessively.			
4	Dig four cuts around the cylinder, carefully, 2-3 cm around the ring.			
5	Extract the core using a spade, preserving the soil clump on top of the cylinder opening.			
6	Remove excess soil using a knife and roots using scissors.			
7	If less than 10% of cylinder is empty, fill with removed soil. If more than 10% is missing, repeat the process			
8	To take the 10-30 cm sample, repeat the same steps for the sampling, after digging to a depth of 20 cm in the place where the first core was taken.			

5th – Check that you have all the necessary samples

C. Stratified sampling approach for montado/Dehesa

1st – Check you have all the required material (the day before)

Before leaving to the field, kindly check the needed materials/steps:

- Check all equipment is clean.
- Calibrate GPS and confirm coordinate system.
- Prepare field data sheets with site IDs and strata.
- Carry extra sample bags, labels, gloves, and marker pens.
- Label bags according to the nomenclature:
 - Arable lands: FarmID_Date_SampleNo_Depth
 - Montado: FarmID_Date_SampleNo_Depth_Canopy(In/Out)
 - Line perennial crops: FarmID_Date_SampleNo_Depth_Line (Row/Interrow)
- Check you have all the required material organized – composite samples

Item	Check
Tablet/map with theoretical coordinates of sampling units	
GPS	
Compass	
Flags/sticks	
Measuring tape of 4m at least	
Soil probe or soil auger with at least 30 cm	
Spade with a 20 cm blade	
Small spade	
Field knife with flat blade	
Stainless steel rings + cylinder holder device	
Rubber mallet	
Permanent marker	
Two labelled reclosable plastic bags per sampling unit	
Two labelled reclosable plastic bags per sampling unit for bulk density	
Disposable laboratory gloves	
Paper towels	
Box to store and transport the samples	

Cooler with ice packs to preserve samples	
Plastic container (bucket)	

Check you have all the required material organized – bulk density (excavation method)

Item	Check
Short level (20cm)	
Annular rigid template (15-20 cm diameter)	
Soup spoon or small gardening shovel	
Transparent, thin, waterproof bags	
Scissors	

Suggested additional material:

Sieves (2 mm) – for field pre-cleaning of coarse fragments.

Spray bottle with ethanol or water – for cleaning tools.

Flag poles or stakes – mark plot centres for revisits.

Notebook / pens / pencils – waterproof types preferred.

Scale (portable) – estimate soil weight per composite.

2nd - Before sampling, take records:

Parameter:	Notes:
Weather	
Soil conditions	
Evidence of recent agricultural practices	

Last recorded agricultural practice	
Thickness of organic horizon	
Have you taken pictures yet? Of what?	

3rd – Establish the lines of trees to be monitored

- Locate the line of five trees closest to the coordinates of the sampling unit that ends inside the strata
- Mark with flags the places for the bulk density determination: one below the canopy of the 3rd tree and another in the segment outside the canopy after that tree.
- Register the coordinates of the beginning and end of the tree-line

Sampling Unit	Point	Latitude	Longitude
Unit 1	Beginning		
	End		
Unit 2	Beginning		
	End		
Unit 3	Beginning		
	End		

- Perform the sampling according to the scheme below, following the tree line beginning and end. Namely collecting:
 - o Two random subsamples under the canopy of each tree. Gather the 10 subsamples in a bag labeled as “inside canopy” – last letter is “I”
 - o Take two random samples at each segment between canopies, extending the last segment after the last tree. Gather the 10 subsamples in a separate bag labelled as “outside canopy” – last letter is “O”

4th – Follow the steps bellow per plot (experimental and control plots, if applicable)

- Ideally the material for collecting samples between sampling units is different/cleaned thoroughly to prevent cross-contamination
- Take at least 500-600g of composite sample

Sampling procedure per sampling unit composite sample:

#	Step	Sampling unit		
		1	2	3
1	Record the real location of the transect			
2	From there, mark the composite sampling sites			
3	Using the auger, sample the composite samples using clockwise motions			
4	Retrieve the horizons the depths separately, between 0-10 cm and 10-30 cm, into corresponding pre-labelled bags			
5	Store the sample in a cooler with ice packs.			

Sampling procedure per sampling unit bulk density/coarse fragments sample and to analyse soil moisture at field water capacity (core method):

#	Step	Sampling unit		
		1	2	3
1	At the marked sites for bulk density sampling Remove organic horizon, as well as stones larger than 6 cm			

2	At the marked sites for bulk density sampling dig a pit for bulk density and coarse fragments. Adapt size of the pit to conditions of the soil. Rake the first two cm of soil away.			
3	Press the cylinder into the 2-10 cm layer of soil until the end. Be careful not to press excessively.			
4	Dig four holes around the cylinder, carefully, 2-3 cm around the ring.			
5	Extract the core using a spade, preserving the soil clump on top of the cylinder opening.			
6	Remove excess soil using a knife and roots using scissors.			
7	If less than 10% of cylinder is empty, fill with removed soil. If more than 10% is missing, repeat the process			
8	To take the 10-30 cm sample, repeat the same steps for the sampling, after digging to a depth of 20 cm in the place where the first core was taken.			

5th – Check that you have all the necessary samples